

Microbial colonization of gypsum: from the fossil record to the present day

Jan Jehlicka^{1,2*}, Aharon Oren³, Petr Vitek⁴, Jacek Wierzbos⁵

¹Institute of Geochemistry, Mineralogy and Mineral Resources, Faculty of Science, Charles University, Czechia, ²Charles University, Czechia, ³Hebrew University of Jerusalem, Israel, ⁴Global Change Research Institute, Czech Academy of Sciences, Czechia, ⁵Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales, Spain

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Scope Statement

The proposed paper will be the first review to provide an overview of the presence of microorganisms and/or their biomarkers in gypsum. Endolithic colonization of gypsum are common and some are well documented. They have been observed through the world including wet (salterns) as well as extremely dry environments (e.g., Atacama Desert). These colonizations occur frequently under extreme conditions. The aim of this review is to introduce the common sulfate mineral gypsum as a possible matrix for colonization by different microorganisms. We give a short overview of approaches and analytical techniques allowing understanding these special situations: developing life in gypsum mineral matrices. Some allow understanding what microorganisms are present, what are the relationships of the organisms within each site. Some of the data are purely microbiological. Knowledge of the distribution of some key biomarkers is also important. Another important proposed issue is to show different modes of conservation of biomarkers in gypsum, e.g., authigenic "fossil" biomarkers in gypsum of Messinian age. The subject is highly relevant for field microbiology and planetary research and exobiology. Some areas of the Mars surface and gypsum is considered as one of the potential targets in the search for traces of life.

Conflict of interest statement

The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest

CRediT Author Statement

Aharon Oren: Conceptualization, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing. Jacek Wierzcchos: Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing. Jan Jehlicka: Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Resources, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing. Petr Vitek: Funding acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing.

Keywords

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Abstract

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Microorganisms inhabiting gypsum have been observed in environments that differ greatly in water availability. Gypsum colonized by microorganisms, including cyanobacteria, eukaryotic algae, and diverse heterotrophic communities, occurs in hot, arid or even hyperarid environments, in cold environments of the Antarctic and Arctic zones, and in saline and hypersaline lakes and ponds where gypsum precipitates. Fossilized microbial remnants preserved in gypsum were also reported. Gypsum protects the endolithic microbial communities against excessive insolation and ultraviolet radiation, while allowing photosynthetically active radiation to penetrate through the mineral substrate. Here, we review the worldwide occurrence of microbially colonized gypsum and the specific properties of gypsum related to its function as a substrate and habitat for microbial life on Earth and possibly beyond. Methods for detecting and characterizing endolithic communities and their biomarkers in gypsum are discussed, including microscopic, spectroscopic, chemical, and molecular biological techniques. The distribution of different microorganisms and their survival within gypsum crystals under different environmental conditions are described. Finally, we discuss gypsum deposits as possible targets for the search for microbial life or its remnants beyond Earth, especially on Mars, where sulfate-rich deposits occur, and propose strategies to detect them during space exploration missions.

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In review

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1 **Jan Jehlička^{1*}, Aharon Oren², Petr Víték³, Jacek Wierzchos⁴**

2 ¹ Faculty of Science, Charles University, Albertov 6, 128 43, Prague, Czech Republic

3 ² Institute of Life Sciences, The Hebrew University of Jerusalem, The Edmond J. Safra Campus,
4 9190401 Jerusalem, Israel

5 ³ Global Change Research Institute of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Bělidla 986/4a, 603 00 Brno,
6 Czech Republic

7 ⁴ Departamento de Biogeoquímica y Ecología Microbiana, Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales,
8 CSIC c/ Serrano 115 dpdo, 28006 Madrid, Spain

9

10 * Correspondence:

11 Jan Jehlička

12 jehlicka@natur.cuni.cz

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14 Abstract

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16 availability. Gypsum colonized by microorganisms, including cyanobacteria, eukaryotic algae, and
17 diverse heterotrophic communities, occurs in hot, arid or even hyperarid environments, in cold
18 environments of the Antarctic and Arctic zones, and in saline and hypersaline lakes and ponds where
19 gypsum precipitates. Fossilized microbial remnants preserved in gypsum were also reported. Gypsum
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21 while allowing photosynthetically active radiation to penetrate through the mineral substrate. Here,
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23 gypsum related to its function as a substrate and habitat for microbial life on Earth and possibly
24 beyond. Methods for detecting and characterizing endolithic communities and their biomarkers in
25 gypsum are discussed, including microscopic, spectroscopic, chemical, and molecular biological
26 techniques. The distribution of different microorganisms and their survival within gypsum crystals
27 under different environmental conditions are described. Finally, we discuss gypsum deposits as
28 possible targets for the search for microbial life or its remnants beyond Earth, especially on Mars,
29 where sulfate-rich deposits occur, and propose strategies to detect them during space exploration
30 missions.

31 1 Introduction

32 Gypsum ($\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) provides a mineral substrate suitable for microbial colonization. On Earth,
33 such colonization is observed in various environments that greatly differ in water availability. As a
34 typical evaporitic mineral, gypsum precipitates, under exogenic conditions, from aqueous solution
35 (Babel, 2004; Warren, 2016). Gypsum may also crystallize from hydrothermal solutions or originate

36 in other non-evaporitic ways (e.g. through weathering of sulfides). It provides microorganisms
37 protection against excessive insolation, including ultraviolet (UV) radiation, while allowing
38 photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) to penetrate through the mineral substrate. Gypsum
39 transparency to PAR is one of the key prerequisites for phototrophic microorganisms to occupy the
40 gypsum substrate (Cockell et al., 2008).

41 Modern environments with dominant gypsum mineralogy that can be characterized as aquatic include
42 the bottom of solar saltern evaporation ponds or native salt water bodies or mudflats. Dry, subaerial
43 gypsum rocks colonized by microorganisms occur in arid to hyperarid hot desert areas, which are
44 considered as extreme and polyextreme, environments (environments in which several abiogenic
45 stressors co-occur). (Figure 1, Supplementary Table 1).

46 Another type of extreme conditions in which gypsum colonization occurs is the cold Arctic and
47 Antarctic environment. Microbial colonization of gypsum can also be found in mild climates,
48 represented mainly by more or less **coarsely crystalline** gypsum deposits. (Figure 1, Supplementary
49 Table 1).

50 Microorganisms thriving on the surface or in the frame of rocks are called lithobionts, epiliths, resp.
51 endoliths. Golubic et al. (1981) suggested the following terminology for endoliths: chasmoendoliths
52 for those colonizing fissures and cracks of the rocks, cryptoendoliths inhabiting porous rocks cavities
53 and euendoliths for microbes actively penetrating (e.g. boring) the interior of rocks.

54 Microbial colonizations of solar saltern evaporation ponds were intensively studied in Eilat, Israel
55 (Oren et al., 1995; Oren et al., 2009). Gypsum containing natural salt lakes, pools in salt pans (called
56 “salar“ in South America or “playa“ in North-American continent) were observed in Australia
57 (Benison and Karmanocky, 2014) and Andean regions in South America (Farías et al., 2014; Farías
58 et al., 2020). Other native aquatic locations are represented by spring mounds in Tunisia (Stivaletta
59 and Barbieri, 2009) and capillary fringes within saline mudflats with shallow groundwater, called
60 sabkhas (Edwards et al., 2006; Vogel et al., 2009; Vogel et al., 2010).

61 Extremely dry gypsum deposits, where water availability for photosynthesis is at its limits for
62 phototrophic microbes were observed in the Atacama Desert, which is considered as the driest place
63 on Earth (Dong et al., 2007; Wierzchos et al., 2011; Wierzchos et al., 2015). Other, less extreme, but
64 still arid environments with colonized gypsum are described from Death Valley, US (Douglas, 2004)
65 and southern Tunisia (Stivaletta et al., 2010). Gypsum often occurs in the form of a soil crust or
66 gypcrete that provide a porous and translucent substrate that may serve as a refuge for microbial life
67 even in the most challenging environments on the planet (Wierzchos et al., 2011; Wierzchos et al.,
68 2015). Besides hot desert conditions, microbial colonization of gypsum was reported from cold
69 environments of the Antarctic peninsula (Hughes and Lawley, 2003) and from Canadian Arctic zones
70 (Parnell et al., 2004, Cockell et al., 2010) (Table 1).

71 In mild climates, outcrops formed by crystalline gypsum represent a favorable substrate for
72 development of microbial communities. This is mainly due to cleavage of translucent gypsum
73 crystals that form a habitat for chasmolithic colonization as described for Messinian gypsum in Italy
74 (Jehlička et al., 2020; Němečková et al., 2020), Israel, and Poland (Němečková et al., 2021;
75 Němečková et al., 2022). Fossilized microbial remnants in gypsum were also reported (Vai and Ricci
76 Lucchi, 1977; Schopf et al., 2012; Cámara et al., 2016), as briefly discussed in the section below on
77 authigenic (fossil) biomarkers (Figure 1, Supplementary Table 1).

78
79

80 This is the first review focused on gypsum occurrences as a substrate and habitat for microbial life on
81 Earth (Figure 1). We describe the analytical approaches used to detect and analyze microbial
82 colonizations in gypsum, and provide a detailed overview of occurrences of microbial colonizations
83 of gypsum in different types of environments. Interaction between rocks and microorganisms is a
84 well-known and widespread phenomenon observed in nature or on man-made buildings, statues, or
85 other artefacts (Macedo et al., 2009; Hauer et al., 2015). Those occur in limestone, marble, sandstone
86 and on different other building stones. Endolithic colonizations of gypsum matrices are less common,
87 but some are well documented. This review focuses on these colonizations as observed and described
88 from very different environments.

89 The aim of this review is to introduce the common sulfate mineral gypsum as a matrix for
90 colonization by different microorganisms. In this review, the broad possibilities of interactions
91 between microorganisms and gypsum from contrasting settings are considered. The complex issue of
92 their survival under extreme conditions is highlighted. The review encompasses gypsum as recently
93 colonized superficially under sub-atmospheric conditions. It also presents halophilic microorganisms
94 that develop in newly formed crystalline bottom gypsum in aquatic environments. The occurrence of
95 fossilized remnants of microorganisms inside gypsum crystals is presented as well. Possibilities of
96 survival of microbes in stones and protective roles of gypsum are of high relevance for astrobiology.

97 We first describe the analytical approaches used to detect and analyze microbial colonization in
98 gypsum. We then provide a detailed overview of occurrences of microbial colonizations of gypsum
99 in different types of environments, with special emphasis on the understanding how endoliths survive
100 in harsh conditions and the evaluation of the origin of the water essential for colonization in arid and
101 hyper-arid conditions. We also review the occurrence of tiny morphological or chemical remnants in
102 gypsum originating from microbiota from the past and address the question to what extent does
103 gypsum contain authigenic fossilized microbes and their biomarkers. Such remnants can be a clue to
104 our understanding of the conditions that prevailed in such marine environments in the past, as well as
105 their changes throughout time. Gypsum is one of evaporitic minerals which locally forms important
106 layers on Mars (e.g. Osterloo et al., 2008). Also on that planet, it is considered as a product of
107 crystallization from water bodies in the remote past. The search for trace biomarkers is of high
108 importance in exobiology, including Martian studies. Therefore, one of the questions addressed in
109 this review is whether trace biomarkers in gypsum could be relevant for the search for life beyond
110 Earth and answer the question: To what extent terrestrial training would help in future extraterrestrial
111 studies.

112 **2. Properties and occurrence of gypsum**

113

114 Gypsum ($\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) is the most common calcium sulfate mineral occurring in sedimentary
115 sequences. Bassanite ($\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 1/2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and anhydrite (CaSO_4) are other calcium sulfate minerals that
116 are stable at higher temperatures. Gypsum and bassanite are monoclinic minerals; in contrast,
117 anhydrite crystallizes as orthorhombic phase. The structure of gypsum consists of layers of SO_4^{2-}
118 tetrahedra, bound together by Ca^{2+} cations. Crystalline water molecules are arranged between these
119 layers.

120 Gypsum is soft (2 on the Mohs scale). Crystalline gypsum has multiple cleavage planes and exhibits
121 perfect cleavage along a plane parallel to both the c-axis and the a-axis. The solubility of gypsum in
122 water is high compared to that of calcite but much lower for halite. Water content in gypsum rocks
123 has important impact on their mechanical properties. This was observed in the frame of studies in

124 more or less weathered gypsum in mines (Auvray et al., 2004) and through laboratory mechanical
125 experiments (Caselle et al., 2022).

126 Gypsum is translucent or transparent, colorless or whitish, but can also be light brown, gray,
127 yellowish, or greenish due to the presence of inclusions or impurities. These optical features, in
128 addition to the structural characteristics, affect the properties of the endolithic habitat.

129 Gypsum occurs in different forms and crystal shapes. Big and transparent crystals are frequently
130 called selenite (from Greek *selēnē*, Moon). The fibrous translucent and opalescent variety with silky
131 luster is called satin spar, the fine-grained variety is named alabaster. Single, well-developed crystals
132 can be prismatic, blocky, tabular, lenseoid or bladed. Twinned crystals are very common, and different
133 modes of twinning gypsum are known: swallowtail on tabular and prismatic crystals commonly found
134 in halite layers, contact twins, and Montmartre twins from clays and sands (Cody and Cody, 1989a;
135 Cody and Cody, 1989b; Jafarzadeh and Burnham, 1992; Van Driessche et al., 2019).

136 Gypsum occurs as a more or less dominant component of sedimentary rock assemblages. Gypsite is
137 the earthy variety; gypsarenite is a term used to designate a sedimentary rock with sand-size gypsum
138 mixed with calcareous and terrigenous clasts (Testa and Lugli, 2000; Warren, 2016). Compact
139 gypcrete with variable crystal size can be of hydrothermal origin. Gypsum has been formed under
140 warm conditions in large areas in the past (Permian e.g. in the Harz area, Germany, Triassic e.g. in
141 the French Alps and especially Tertiary in Italy). In the Mediterranean area, gypsum rocks form huge
142 volumes of the geological basement and can be sampled and studied in drill cores. Here, important
143 volumes of salts (halite and gypsum) were deposited in Tertiary Messinian ages (7.2-5.3 Ma). In
144 several areas of the Mediterranean region (Italy, Sicily, Spain, Rhodos, Turkey), superficial gypsum
145 outcrops are exposed to atmospheric conditions. Gypsum-exposed formations, frequently in form of
146 gypsum crusts covering the desert soil (regolith) surface, also occur in desertic zones of the Namib
147 Desert (Africa) and the Atacama Desert (Chile).

148 Gypsum is found in extensive beds formed by the evaporation of ocean brine. Nowadays it
149 crystallizes in natural environments (sabkhas, salars, salt lakes) and in evaporation ponds of man-
150 made salterns. It also occurs as a weathering product of sulfides in ore or volcanic deposits. Today
151 gypsum precipitation occurs in evaporitic areas in sabkhas of the Mediterranean coast of Egypt, salt
152 lakes in South Australia (Warren, 1982) and India (Sinha and Raymahashay, 2004), salars of the
153 Atacama Desert (Farías et al., 2014) and the high Andes (Benison and Karmanocky, 2014). However,
154 the present-day evaporitic environments sites are small compared to the massive salt deposits formed
155 during past geological times (Warren, 2010).

156 Gypsum is generally considered a typical evaporitic mineral; however, non-evaporitic gypsum
157 formation also occurs in marine sediments due to mixing of seawater coupled to the dissolution of
158 foraminiferal ooze (Briskin and Schreiber, 1978), salt diapirism (Haffert and Haeckel 2019),
159 oxidation of sedimentary sulfide minerals in carbonate-rich sediments (Pirlet et al., 2010), gas
160 hydrate formation (Wang et al., 2004), and seeping of brines (Huguen et al., 2009). Spectacular giant
161 gypsum crystals formed through hydrothermal processes are found in the Naica Mine (Mexico)
162 (García-Ruiz et al., 2007). Under terrestrial evaporitic conditions, gypsum is the dominant calcium
163 sulfate primary phase (Ossorio et al., 2014). In very arid and hot environments such as sabkhas,
164 anhydrite has been reported to directly form at the surface from concentrated brines or replacing
165 gypsum (Aref et al., 2018). Compared to gypsum and anhydrite, bassanite deposits are very scarce in
166 the geological record, because this mineral readily transforms into gypsum when in contact with
167 water or in a humid environment (Warren, 2016).

168

169 3. Detecting microorganisms and microbial biosignatures in gypsum

170 The first step in the characterization of microbial endolithic colonization within the mineral substrate
171 is to detect it. Often this is not a trivial task: "*On first impression the habitat seems as sterile as the*
172 *surface of the autoclaved glass but the trained eye, aided by the microscope, sees otherwise*"
173 (Wilson, 2003). Cyanobacteria and other phototrophic microorganisms inhabiting gypsum outcrops
174 or developing in gypsum aggregates on the bottom of salterns are commonly colorful due to their
175 pigments. Frequently, even the naked eye can detect these colorful microbial colonization layers
176 (Figure 2).

177 Supplementary Table 2 summarizes the analytical approaches that can be deployed.

178

179 3.1 Microscopic techniques

180 The next step in detecting microorganisms in gypsum should be the application of microscopy
181 investigation strategies. The easiest way is examining scraped material by optical microscopy (OM)
182 using bright field and/or diffraction interference contrast (DIC) microscopy. This approach enables
183 immediate visualization of many of the components of the microbial community. However, the
184 separation of microbial components from the intact lithic substrate results in a significant loss of
185 information related to the location of the microbial communities within the rock and their
186 organization. Additionally, the relatively low-resolution of OM techniques precludes a detailed
187 characterization of the microorganisms and minerals on which they adhere.

188 To improve resolution and for *in situ* (within the natural endolithic habitats) characterization
189 of endolithic microbial communities, a Scanning Electron Microscope can be used in the Secondary
190 Electron (SEM-SE) visualization mode. However, SEM-SE images only provide topographic and
191 morphological information, while in most cases the identification of specific microorganisms
192 becomes impossible. Additionally, extracellular polymeric substances (EPS) cover many of the
193 microorganisms and their aggregates, hiding elements of microbial consortia. Therefore, Wierzchos
194 and Ascaso (1994) introduced a novel investigation strategy based on a Scanning Electron
195 Microscope working in Backscattered Electrons (SEM-BSE) mode for *in situ* detailed visualization
196 and characterization of lithobiontic microorganisms and their spatial relationships can be
197 distinguished (Figure 3). Examples of visualization and characterization of endolithic microbial
198 communities within gypsum rocks are shown in Figures 3 A-F. Detailed description of the SEM-BSE
199 methodology was given by Wierzchos and Ascaso (1994), Wierzchos et al. (2011), and Wierzchos et
200 al. (2015).

201 For some scientific goals, visualization of the internal micromorphology of microbial cells in their
202 natural hydrated state is required. In these cases, Low Temperature Scanning Electron Microscopy
203 (LT-SEM) yielded remarkable results. The cryo-fractured samples allow visualization of
204 ultrastructural elements of microbial cells and their *in situ* identification (Wierzchos et al., 2015).
205 Figures 3G and 3H show examples of LT-SEM application for the detection and characterization of
206 gypsum endoliths. Environmental Scanning Electron Microscope (ESEM) is a technique that allows
207 the study of the hydration state of endolithic microorganisms without any preparation procedure.
208 Using ESEM, water vapor absorption by endolithic microorganisms may be assessed by varying the
209 relative humidity within the ESEM chamber (Wierzchos et al., 2011). An example of the
210 visualization of endolithic cyanobacteria aggregates in their natural hydration state using this
211 technique is shown in Figure 3I. Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) is commonly applied for
212 high-resolution characterization of cell ultrastructure and of the minerals adhered to the microbial

213 colonies (Figure 3M). Chlorophyll and/or phycobiliprotein pigments emit autofluorescence signals.
214 Fluorescent Microscopy (FM) can easily detect these signals in living cells of chlorophyll containing
215 phototrophs. Moreover, FM allows detection of autofluorescence signals originating from
216 biomolecules after cell decay or degradation processes. Specific staining using fluorochromes that
217 stain DNA allows detection of heterotrophic bacteria and nuclei of eukaryotic microorganisms, as
218 shown in Figure 3K. The resolution of FM images can be improved using Confocal Laser Scanning
219 Microscopy (CLSM), where 3D reconstructed images provide significant information about the
220 spatial organization and distribution of cells within microbial aggregates (Figure 3L).

221

222 **3.2 Spectroscopic techniques**

223 Several spectroscopic analytical tools were tested to evaluate their performance and limits for
224 detecting biomarkers in mineral matrices including gypsum (Stromberg et al., 2014, Cloutis et al.,
225 2021). Chlorophyll *a* and carotenoids were detected in endoliths in gypsum from the impact crater
226 Lake St Martin (Canada) by reflectance spectroscopy (Rhind et al., 2014; Figure 2F). Using Visible
227 Near infrared (Vis-NIR) spectroscopy, Preston et al. (2020) detected chlorophyll and possibly
228 carotenoids in gypsum collected from the hypersaline Tirez Lake in Spain.

229 Raman spectrometry is commonly applied for detection and identification of biomarkers within
230 mineral matrices. It is a valuable tool for nondestructive analysis of biomolecules derived from extant
231 and fossil microbes (Marshall et al., 2006), as well as living microbial communities inhabiting rocks
232 (endoliths) (Russell et al., 1998; Wynn-Williams and Edwards 2000a; Wynn-Williams and Edwards
233 2000b; Edwards et al., 2005a; Jorge Villar et al., 2005a; Jorge Villar et al., 2005b). The technique
234 allows to obtain simultaneous chemical information about the studied microbial colonization and the
235 host mineral matrix forming the rock habitat. Raman spectroscopy is particularly suitable for the
236 detection of photosynthetic and photoprotective pigments of microorganisms (Jehlička et al., 2014;
237 Jehlička and Oren, 2013). As detected in gypsum, these include light-harvesting pigments such as
238 chlorophyll, phycobiliproteins, carotenoids belonging to cyanobacteria and algae (Vítek et al., 2013),
239 and protective pigments such as scytonemin (Vítek et al., 2016; Nemečková et al., 2021), scytonin
240 (Edwards et al., 2023) and gloeocapsin (Storme et al., 2015; Nemečková et al., 2021; Nemečková et
241 al., 2022; Lara et al., 2022). The spectroscopic information obtained in these studies and the
242 assignment of the spectral signatures from gypsum endoliths to pigments of given groups of
243 microorganisms now serve as reference data for further studies in the fields of microbiology,
244 geobiology, and astrobiology (Supplementary Table 3). Raman microspectrometry allows to detect
245 traces of compounds of interest in inclusions within transparent halite, gypsum, and other evaporitic
246 minerals (Winters et al., 2013; Jehlička et al., 2018) and to characterize amorphous carbon of
247 fossilised material in Messinian selenitic gypsum (Pellegrino et al. 2021).

248 Portable battery-charged handheld Raman spectrometers, developed in recent years, can be deployed
249 outdoors, even under hostile conditions in the field (Culka et al., 2011; Culka et al., 2014; Vítek et
250 al., 2014). Their possibilities and limitations in geoscience (including astrobiology) and
251 geomicrobiology were reviewed by Vandenberg et al. (2014) and by Jehlička and Culka (2022).
252 Such tools were first equipped with 785 nm excitation diode lasers. More recently, use of green lasers
253 (532 nm) permits enhanced possibilities of detecting and studying e.g. carotenoid pigments (Culka et
254 al., 2022), including in gypsum colonizations (Culka et al., 2014). Other studies using these miniature
255 tools are reported in Supplementary Table 3.

256 Beyond the classical point spectral analysis, Raman spectroscopy allows for surface imaging,
257 resulting in chemical maps (Vítek et al., 2016; Figures 2B, 2C). An analysis of the imaging dataset of

258 a microbial colony inhabiting gypcrete from the Atacama Desert aided to rule out the presence of
259 different hydration states of Ca-sulfate, i.e., anhydrite and bassanite, in the studied material (Vítek et
260 al., 2016; see further the section ‘Can crystallization water of gypsum support life of endolithic
261 communities?’). Two major approaches of scanning by the Raman microscope are point mapping and
262 line mapping. For gypsum samples from hot deserts, the Raman imaging method was first applied by
263 Wierzchos et al. (2015). The authors described gypcretes from the Atacama Desert, predominantly
264 colonized by cyanobacteria, heterotrophic bacteria, and algae. Raman mapping allowed to visualize
265 the distribution of carotenoids in the cryptoendolithic colonization layer dominated by algae.
266 Enhancement of the carotenoid Raman signal intensity close to the surface was registered, which was
267 interpreted as an adaptation mechanism to excessive solar irradiation. In addition, cyanobacteria,
268 found at deeper below gypsum surface, synthesized scytonemin as a passive UV-screening pigment.
269 The Raman imaging allowed to visualize the distribution of the scytonemin simultaneously with
270 chemistry of the surrounding mineral matrix (Vítek et al., 2016). The adaptation strategies of the
271 endolithic colonies in gypsum from the Atacama Desert, based on gradients of biomolecular
272 responses as detected by Raman spectroscopy were distinguished and described by Vítek and
273 Wierzchos (2020).

274

275 **3.3 Chemical analysis of microbial pigments and other biomarkers**

276 Analysis of organic extracts prepared from sedimentary rocks, including gypsum, belongs to the
277 traditional organic geochemistry approaches. Pigments and other biomarkers within recent
278 colonizations of rocky outcrops as well as fossil residues dispersed in rocks can be studied by this
279 approach, using analytical methods such as high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) and
280 liquid chromatography with tandem mass spectrometry (LC MS-MS) (Squier et al., 2002; Castaneda
281 and Schouten, 2011). Villanueva et al. (1994) made a detailed HPLC study of carotenoids and
282 chlorins in microbial mats from calcite and calcite/gypsum evaporitic environments of the solar
283 salterns of Les Salines de la Trinitat, located in the Ebro Delta, Spain. Oren et al. (1995) documented
284 the distribution of carotenoids myxoxanthophyll, echinenone and canthaxanthin (important mainly in
285 the orange-brown layer), as well as bacteriochlorophyll *a* and carotenoids of the spirilloxanthin series
286 derived from photosynthetic purple sulfur bacteria in gypsum crusts of the salterns of Eilat, Israel
287 (Figure 2D). Other studies focusing on describing distribution of biomarkers including pigments and
288 lipids in gypsum are reported in Supplementary Table 3.

289 Gypsum from the Messinian (Tertiary age) in Mediterranean sedimentary sequences sometimes
290 contain fossilized organic matter. In a pioneering study, ten Haven et al., (1985) analyzed organic
291 extracts from gypsum and marls originating from the Perticara basin (Romagna Marche Messinian
292 evaporitic basin, Italy). Isorenieratene was repeatedly and consistently detected using HPLC and MS
293 in extracts of marls of the Miocene Gessoso-solfifera Formation of the Vena del Gesso basin (Italy)
294 (Keely et al., 1995). More recent approaches using dedicated GC-MS instrumentation allow to
295 deepen our knowledge on these occurrences from different sites of Messinian gypsum: studying
296 halophiles in Calcare di Base (Sicily, Calabria) (Birgel et al., 2014), sedimentary gypsum in the
297 Piedmont basin (Natalicchio et al., 2017), in the Nijar Basin, in Vena del Gesso (Northern Italy),
298 Crete and Cyprus (Natalicchio et al., 2022) and in the Govone section in NW Italy (Sabino et al.,
299 2020).

300 **To summarize, it can be understood that modern analytical tools, wheter chemical or spectroscopic**
301 **bring important information on microbial colonizations, microorganisms themselves and their**
302 **survival in gypsum matrix. Visualization through microscopies can be of high relevance and**
303 **excellent insight can be obtained mainly through combining methods.**

304 3.4 Characterization of gypsum-associated microbial communities using gene sequence data

305 Cultivation-independent approaches toward the characterization of the microbial communities of
306 gypsum deposits have been applied to samples from many sites worldwide. Supplementary Table 4
307 summarizes the results. Most of those studies used small genes as phylogenetic marker (16S rRNA
308 for prokaryotes, 18S rRNA for eukaryotes). Others targeted functional genes such as *nifH* for
309 nitrogen fixation (López-Lozano et al., 2012), *dsrAB* for dissimilatory sulfate reduction, and *mcr* for
310 methanogenesis (Sørensen et al., 2009). Metagenomics techniques were recently used in a study of a
311 gypsum crust in the Atacama Desert, Chile (Schulze-Makuch et al., 2021). Abundance of
312 Methylophilales, Rhizobiales, Caulobacterales, and Pseudomonadales suggests that a methylotrophic
313 community may have existed in the crusts.

314 16S rRNA genes affiliated with the cyanobacterial genus *Chroococidiopsis* were found in
315 nearly all dry gypsum environments examined. In aquatic systems, the most frequently encountered
316 cyanobacterial 16S rRNA genes belonged to the unicellular *Euhalothece* group and to filamentous
317 types such as *Leptolyngbya*, *Phormidium*, *Halospirulina* and *Geitlerinema*. Of particular interest is
318 the recovery of partial 16S rRNA gene fragments affiliated with *Geitlerinema*, *Chroococidiopsis*
319 and *Lyngbya* from primary late Miocene (5.8-5.9 Ma) gypsum from the Apennines (Italy), showing
320 that DNA can be preserved in gypsum for very long times. The genes were 94-99% identical to those
321 of known modern modern representatives of these genera (Panieri et al., 2010).

322 Different groups of anoxygenic phototrophic bacteria were identified in the 16S rRNA gene
323 libraries of gypsum deposits in aquatic systems. These often include members of the
324 *Gammaproteobacteria* (*Chromatiaceae*, *Ectothiorhodospiraceae*). *Rhodovibrio*
325 (*Alphaproteobacteria*) sequences were enriched in the upper gypsum sediments of the Bonneville
326 Salt Flats (Utah, USA) (McGonigle et al., 2019). Members of the *Chloroflexota* were shown to be
327 associated with benthic gypsum crusts at Guerrero Negro, Mexico (Jahnke et al., 2014) and Eilat,
328 Israel (Sørensen et al., 2005). Anoxygenic phototrophs of the phylum *Chlorobiota* were also found at
329 Guerrero Negro (Jahnke et al., 2014).

330 Many groups of heterotrophic bacteria are associated with dry gypsum rocks and aquatic
331 gypsum deposits. 16S rRNA gene sequences of *Pseudomonadota*, *Actinomycetota*, and *Bacteroidota*
332 were found everywhere, often accompanied by members of the *Gemmatimonadota*, *Planctomycetota*,
333 *Bacillota*, and other bacterial phyla (for references see the last column of Supplementary Table 4).
334 Archaea generally contribute only a minor part of the total prokaryotic 16S rRNA gene sequences
335 recovered from gypsum environments.

336 Sequencing small subunit rRNA genes has yielded a good overview of the phylogenetic
337 diversity within microbial communities inhabiting gypsum. However, molecular approaches toward
338 the understanding of the functioning of the microbial ecosystems, using metagenomics,
339 metatranscriptomics, metaproteomics or by targeting key functional genes, have been little used thus
340 far.

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346 **4. A worldwide survey of colonized gypsum occurrences.**

347 The sections below document the distribution of gypsum colonized by microorganisms in various
348 types of environments (Figure 1, Supplementary Table 1 and Table 1) In many climatic regimes, rock
349 surfaces exposed to the atmosphere become colonized by epilithic microbial communities, forming
350 subaerial biofilms (Gorbushina, 2007). These biofilms are characterized by patchy growth,
351 dominated by associations of fungi, algae, cyanobacteria, heterotrophic bacteria and lichens. Such
352 epilithic colonization is frequently found under mild (Gorbushina, 2007) but also under extreme
353 climatic conditions (Wierzchos et al., 2011). Epilithic microorganisms are exposed to solar radiation
354 and need protection against harmful UV irradiance. Many therefore synthesize special dark UV
355 protective pigments like scytonemin, scytonin or gloeocapsin (Proteau et al., 1993; Bultel-Poncé et
356 al., 2004; Storme et al., 2015; Jehlička et al., 2023).

357 When the characteristics of the rocks are suitable, microorganism may proliferate inside the
358 rocks, forming endolithic microbial communities adapted to life below the rock surface. Such
359 endolithic communities are found in different climatic regimes (Table 1). Microorganisms may
360 develop within micrometric pores of rocks beneath the rock surface (cryptoendolithic habitats), in
361 irregular cracks or in flat spaces in the frame of rock cleavage (chasmoendolithic habitats), within
362 pores at the bottom part of the rock (hypoendolithic habitats) (Wierzchos et al., 2018), or within
363 pores actively bored by the microorganisms (euendolithic habitats). Development of such endolithic
364 colonizations appears to be especially critically driven by the availability of water retained by the
365 rocks and by diffusion of light inside the rocks. The complex network of pores in gypsum-bearing
366 rocks and the perfect cleavage in tabular crystalline aggregates of selenite play important roles in
367 liquid water retention. The optical properties of gypsum, including light transmittance by transparent
368 crystals or their aggregates allow light to be available for photosynthesis in the deeper layers, while
369 harmful UV radiation is attenuated by gypsum shielding. Figure 4 conceptually illustrates how these
370 endolithic microbial communities are organized within the crypto- chasmo- and hypoendolithic
371 habitats in gypsum deposits. These three different endolithic microhabitats were identified and
372 characterized in gypcrete at the same site, each with a particular architecture, and found at the
373 microscale within the same piece of gypcrete (Wierzchos et al., 2015).

374

375 **4.1 Subaerial occurrences - outcrops**

376 Gypsum occurring in landscape as superficial outcrops represents an ideal environment for microbial
377 colonization. Due to its physical and mineralogical properties, endolithic colonizations of gypsum
378 appear to be more common compared to limestone or magmatic and metamorphic rocks. Gypsum of
379 Messinian age occurs as important layers, blocks and outcrops in a few areas in Italy (Apennines,
380 Sicily; Figure 2G). Epilithic growth especially of lichens on the surface of gypsum outcrops, gypsum
381 boulders or gypsum soils was reported from the Messinian gypsum strip in the Apennines, south-east
382 of Bologna (Nimis et al., 1996). Differences in the kinds of observed lichens compared to those
383 described from similar sites in Spain and Morocco reflect the more humid and rainy climate in the
384 investigated Italian zone.

385 Raman spectroscopy was used to characterize pigments belonging to coccoid cyanobacteria
386 (*Chroococcidiopsis* sp., *Gloeocapsopsis pleurocapsoides*, *Gloeocapsa compacta*, and *Synechococcus*
387 *sciophilus*), filamentous heterocystous *Nostoc* sp., and filamentous bundle-forming *Symplocastrum*
388 cf. *aurantiacum* and *Microcoleus* sp. in endoliths in gypsum from different sites in Sicily (Jehlička et
389 al., 2020). A portable lightweight Raman spectrometer enabled detection of pigments under field
390 conditions onsite at sites from southern Italy, including Siculana Marina, Santa Elisabetta and

391 Ravanusa (Němečková et al., 2020; Němečková et al., 2022). Using light microscopy and small
392 subunit rRNA gene sequencing, endolithic phototrophs were characterized in gypsum from Sicilian
393 sites. The communities were dominated by cyanobacteria (65.9% on average).
394 *Chroococciopsidaceae* and *Thermosynechococcaceae* were the most abundant cyanobacterial
395 families. In addition, members of *Leptolyngbyaceae*, *Nostocaceae* and *Gloeobacteraceae* were
396 found. Among those, dark pigmented *Nostoc* sp. and *Gloeocapsa compacta* were the most abundant
397 species (Figures 2H, 2I) (Němečková et al., 2023).

398 Other areas of common algal and cyanobacterial epilithic and endolithic colonies in gypsum
399 are situated in eastern Poland. There, important areas of outcropping rocks as well as karstic
400 subsurface consist of gypsum of Badenian (Tertiary) age. The area has a moderate central European
401 climate without extremes, with annual rain up to 900 mm. Microbial pigments were detected at sites
402 of Badenian gypsum (Chwalowice, Skorocice, Chotel Cierwony), using a Raman microspectrometer
403 and a portable Raman spectrometer (Němečková et al., 2021; Němečková et al., 2022). At Nahal
404 Hagal (Galilee, northern Israel), the surface of massive meter-large gypsum blocks contain zones of
405 subsurface endolithic colonizations of cyanobacterial consortia, dominated by *Gloeocapsa* sp. These
406 microbial colonies develop under a relatively dry but not extreme climate with occasional winter
407 rains and moderate temperatures (Němečková et al., 2021). The gypsum shards near Bad Sachsa
408 (Germany) show an endolithic blue-green layer consisting of cyanobacteria and other
409 microorganisms. These were characterized by cultivation of isolated strains, followed by their
410 identification using molecular techniques (Boison et al., 2004).

411 Extensive studies have been made of the abundant endolithic microbial communities in polar
412 and subarctic environments. An endolithic microbial habitat was described from the climatically
413 extreme Alexander Island, Antarctic Peninsula. Optical microscopy, SEM-SE, and CLSM, as well as
414 molecular biological identification methods were used to characterize the cryptoendolithic colonies
415 of cyanobacteria, bacteria and fungi within the translucent gypsum crust that forms on the surface of
416 sandstone boulders (Hughes and Lawley, 2003). Chasmoendolithic cyanobacterial colonization
417 within the cracks and fissures of translucent large selenite crystals was also described in
418 hydrothermal gypsum deposits in the Haughton impact structure, located in a polar desert
419 environment on Devon Island, Canada (Parnell et al., 2004). Colonies detected by optical microscopy
420 occur as masses along cleavage planes, up to 5 cm from the crystal margins. The same Haughton
421 impact structure also contains weathered and remobilized gypsum from exposed mid-Ordovician
422 marine evaporite beds. These gypsum deposits are colonized by cryptoendolithic green zones of
423 cyanobacteria (dominated by *Gloeocapsa/Aphanothece* and *Chroococciopsis* spp. morphotypes)
424 and abundant black zones, visible from the surface, that contain pigmented cyanobacteria and fungi
425 (Cockell et al., 2010). In another zone of the Canadian polar desert (Gypsum Hill, western Axel
426 Heiberg Island), heavily weathered evaporitic gypsum deposits were found to contain a
427 cryptoendolithic viable and active microbial community (Ziolkowski et al., 2013a). This colonization
428 was characterized by optical and fluorescent microscopy and SEM-SE. 16S/18S/23S rRNA pyrotag
429 sequencing demonstrated the presence of a diverse community of phototrophic and heterotrophic
430 bacteria, archaea, algae and fungi. The phototrophic bacterial community was dominated by
431 cyanobacteria, microbial heterotrophs were dominated by *Alphaproteobacteria*, *Betaproteobacteria*
432 and *Actinomycetota*. The heavily weathered gypsum rocks were also colonized by an epilithic lichen
433 community; however, fungal sequences were also recovered from the endolithic region that contained
434 a diversity of fungal species with an abundance of lichenizing Ascomycota, of which 35% were
435 endolithic Verrucariales.

436 To detect the gypsum-hosted endolithic microbial communities of the Lake St. Martin impact
437 structure (Manitoba, Canada; Figure 2F), reflectance spectroscopy, ultraviolet-induced fluorescence

438 spectroscopy and Raman spectroscopy were used. The interior space of gypsum outcrops shows
439 unique endolithic signatures. 16S rRNA gene sequencing of the DNA extracted from the material
440 showed dominance of *Chloroflexota* (Rhind et al., 2014).

441 Endolithic microbial communities, protected against UV radiation and desiccation within
442 microporous translucent gypsum evaporite crusts were also studied in arid areas of southern Tunisia
443 using optical microscopy, ESEM, SEM-SE (Stivaletta and Barbieri 2009), HPLC of extracted
444 pigments and using molecular methods based on the amplification, cloning and sequencing of small-
445 subunit ribosomal RNA (SSU rRNA) genes by Stivaletta et al. (2010).

446

447 In the past decade, endolithic microbial life was discovered in one of the most challenging
448 environments for the survival of life: the hyperarid core of the Atacama Desert in Chile (Wierzchos
449 et al., 2018). The extreme dryness of this area is caused by its location between two mountain ranges,
450 the Andes to the east and the Coastal Cordillera to the west, which prevents the acquisition of
451 moisture from the east and west coasts of the South American continent. The core part of the desert is
452 considered the driest place on Earth (McKay et al., 2003). In addition to its extreme dryness, the
453 Atacama Desert holds records for the highest surface ultraviolet (UV) radiation and total solar
454 irradiance ever measured on Earth. Gypsum crusts covering the Atacama's desert soils and gypcrete
455 (an evaporitic rock mainly composed of gypsum) of hydrothermal origin have been found to harbor
456 endoliths (Figures 2A, 2B). Cyanobacteria with *Chroococcidiopsis* being the dominant genus live in
457 gypsum crusts from Llano de la Paciencia located north of the Salar de Atacama (Dong et al., 2007).
458 Wierzchos et al., (2011) described the colonization of the Ca-sulfate crust with prevailing gypsum
459 phase from the Tarapacá region of the hyperarid zone of the desert. They used a combination of
460 various techniques based on SEM-BSE, ESEM and optical and fluorescent microscopy to describe
461 the cryptoendolithic habitats containing associations of algae and fungi as well as non-lichenized
462 algae, melanized fungi, cyanobacteria, and heterotrophic bacteria. In some of these crusts, novel
463 observations of hypoendolithic habitats were made in which pore spaces are not close to the gypsum
464 crust surface but occur on the underside of the crust which make contact with the underlying soil.
465 These pore spaces were colonized by associations of algae and fungi. The photoautotrophic
466 community from the same crust was later examined using a combination of Raman spectroscopy and
467 optical, fluorescence and SEM-BSE microscopy (Vítek et al., 2013). The Raman data revealed clear
468 differences in pigment composition when comparing the two main groups of photoautotrophs.
469 Differences in carotenoid composition were observed, and strong features of phycobiliproteins were
470 detected within the cyanobacterial colonies, with a substantial decrease of the Raman signal of these
471 accessory pigments in decayed cells.

472 The carbon turnover rate by the endoliths colonizing gypcrete from the Monturaqui meteorite
473 impact crater region, Chile, was also studied. Stable carbon isotope analysis of phospholipid fatty
474 acids and glycolipid fatty acids of the microbial membranes indicated that present-day atmospheric
475 carbon is assimilated into the microbial community biomass. $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ measurements suggested that
476 autotrophy and/or quantitative conversion of organic matter to CO_2 are the dominant processes
477 occurring within the rock (Ziolkowski et al., 2013b).

478 DiRuggiero et al. (2013) described chasmoendolithic colonization of the fissures of rhyolite-
479 gypsum rocks in the Lomas de Tilocalar region. The chasmoendolithic communities were dominated
480 by cyanobacteria (*Chroococcidiopsis* spp.) and supported a number of heterotrophic bacterial
481 lineages, mainly belonging to the phylum *Actinomycetota* and the class *Alphaproteobacteria*. Culka
482 et al., (2017) studied cryptoendolithic microbial communities composed of eukaryotic
483 microorganisms (melanized fungi and algae) colonizing the interior of gypsum crusts in the hyperarid

484 zone of the Atacama Desert (Salar de Navidad). Fungi and algae were characterized by optical
485 microscopy of thin sections, and a fungal culture was obtained that was identified as
486 *Neocatenulostroma* sp. based on phylogenetic analysis. Melanin pigments from fungal cell walls
487 were for the first time studied by Raman microspectroscopy.

488 Endolithic microbial communities colonize the gypcrete rocks found in the Preandean zone of
489 the Atacama Desert (Wierzchos et al., 2015). These authors used several microscopy techniques and
490 spectroscopic analytical methods combined with molecular analyses to characterize the crypto-,
491 chasmo-, and hypendolithic habitats within gypcrete. Cryptoendolithic colonization showed a
492 succession of organized horizons of algae and cyanobacteria. The presence of cyanobacteria beneath
493 the algal layer, in close contact with sepiolite inclusions, and their hypendolithic colonization
494 suggest that liquid water might occasionally persist within these sub-microhabitats. This study
495 illustrates that successful microbial colonization is the result of a combination of adaptive strategies
496 to avoid excess solar irradiance and extreme evapotranspiration rates, taking advantage of the
497 complex structural and mineralogical characteristics of gypsum deposits—conceptually called “rock's
498 habitable architecture.” Furthermore, self-protection by synthesis and accumulation of secondary
499 metabolites as abundant carotenoids in the upper cryptoendolithic algal habitat and scytonemin in the
500 cyanobacterial hypendolithic habitat likely produces a shielding effect that prevents photoinhibition
501 to the phototrophs, representing another level of adaptation. Figure 4 conceptually illustrates how
502 these endolithic microbial communities are organized in gypsum deposits. Casero et al. (2021)
503 showed that at the microscale within the same piece of gypcrete the differences in the architecture
504 among microhabitats play an essential role in shaping the diversity and composition of endolithic
505 microbial communities.

506 **From this overview it can be seen that gypsum outcrops in different areas worldwide are distributed**
507 **under today's very different climates. Interestingly, studies report microbial colonizations from**
508 **gypsum outcrops under common and extreme settings. Different modes of protecting microbes are**
509 **enabled due to physical and chemical properties of gypsum.**

510 **4.2 Water availability for gypsum colonized endoliths in hyperarid environments**

511 In moderate climatic zones, rainfall is the main source of liquid water for endolithic ecosystems.
512 However, the key importance of dewfall as a water source has been reported for hyperarid areas
513 where other water resources are highly limited (DiRuggiero et al., 2013, Casero et al., 2021). One of
514 the most important sources of moisture for endolithic communities is the condensation of water vapor
515 during the night, dewfall and absorption of this liquid water by the pore system (Casero et al., 2021).
516 The frequency, duration, and abundance of dewfall water depend on atmospheric conditions, such as
517 air relative humidity (air dew point conditions) and air temperature. Moreover, the dewfall frequency
518 and intensity on rock surfaces also depend on the thermal conductivity of rocks and minerals
519 (DiRuggiero et al., 2013; Meslier et al., 2018). This property can significantly decrease the rock
520 surface temperature to lower than the air temperature and can lead to dewdrop formation. Casero et
521 al. (2021) reported how the dewfall water might provide liquid water to chasmoendolithic
522 microorganisms in gypsum substrates in the Atacama Desert.

523

524 Water is available to endolithic microbes in gypsum crusts in the hyperarid Atacama Desert mainly
525 due to water microdroplets deposited during dewfall events. The droplets deposited on the surface
526 during night/early morning infiltrate the crust by gravity and capillary suction through intercrystalline
527 spaces. This water can be retained within the pores for several hours and may cause dissolution of
528 gypsum, relocation of ions, and later gypsum recrystallization during daytime evaporation. These

529 moist conditions are appropriate for organomineralization processes inside the Ca-sulfate crust,
530 allowing for the formation of biosignatures and microfossils. Such traces of microbial extinct life
531 were detected within the gypsum crusts in the form of calcium carbonate precipitates around
532 remnants of cryptoendolithic algae, as well as remaining algal cells permineralized by Mg-Si-rich
533 minerals and web-like structures within the hypoendolithic cyanobacterial habitat via
534 permineralization of extracellular polymeric substances (Cámara et al., 2016). The south area of the
535 Tarapacá region is hyperarid because scarce rains and extremely high rates of evapotranspiration, but
536 this zone is also considered as a 'foggy environment' (Cereceda et al., 2008). This region reveals a
537 high biodiversity, even of vascular plants, and epilithic lichens cover the gypsum crusts colonized
538 also by endolithic microbial communities (Wierzchos et al., 2011).

539 However, Ertekin et al. (2021) claimed that it was not water availability but the gypsum rock
540 structure that drove the taxonomic and functional diversity of endolithic microbial communities in
541 this fog oasis environment. Ertekin et al. (2021) compared the structure (measured by X-ray
542 computed tomography, CT scan) and endoliths biodiversity (by high-throughput amplicon and
543 metagenome sequencing) from gypsum crusts in the Tarapacá (KM in Ertekin et al., 2021) and
544 gypcrete rocks in the Preandean part of the Atacama Desert (Cordon de Lila – Monturaqui (CL-
545 MTQ)) distant of 400 km southeast. Communities inhabiting the Tarapacá gypsum crust with a more
546 fragmented substrate architecture had higher taxonomic and functional diversity, and this was
547 attributed to the lower water availability (Ertekin et al., 2021). However, Ertekin et al. (2021) devoted
548 insufficient attention to microclimatic data that indicate that, despite certain differences in gypsum
549 rock architecture, the numbers of hours when relative humidity of air exceeded 60% was 13-fold
550 higher in Tarapacá than in the Cordon de Lila region (Ertekin et al., 2021; Wierzchos et al., 2011;
551 Wierzchos et al., 2015). The mean annual RH for Tarapacá is 48.0%, while the Cordon de Lila -
552 Monturaqui region is extremely arid with a mean annual RH of 16.5%, resulting in the virtual
553 absence of any life form on its rocks and soil surfaces (Wierzchos et al., 2015). Moreover, two-
554 samples *t*-test analyses (ANOVA) of temperature (T) and relative humidity (RH) for both sampling
555 zones show (Cyprus 1) that adjusted *P*-values were <0.001, indicating significant differences of
556 climatic parameters for the sampling zones mentioned by Ertekin et al. (2021). Differences in
557 taxonomic and functional diversity of endolithic microbial communities between the gypsum crust
558 (Tarapacá) and gypcrete (Preandean zone) are expected. However, the two sites differ greatly in
559 microclimatic characteristics and aridity, and therefore in water availability. Significant differences
560 of water vapour content in the atmosphere and facility of dewfall formation conditions thus explain
561 the differences in taxonomic and functional diversity of the endolithic microbial communities within
562 gypsum rocks in the Atacama Desert.

563 **4.3 Can crystallization water of gypsum support life of endolithic communities?**

564 The idea that crystallization water of gypsum could be available to living organisms was first
565 suggested for plants growing in arid areas by Palacio et al. (2014) and De La Puente et al. (2022).
566 These authors characterized the water stable isotope composition, $\delta^2\text{H}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$, of the plants' xylem
567 water and related it to the free and gypsum crystallization water extracted from different depths
568 throughout the soil profile and the groundwater in both spring and summer. Bayesian isotope mixing
569 models were used to estimate the contribution of water sources to plant xylem sap. Both papers
570 concluded that crystallization water of gypsum ($\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) extracted by plants represents a
571 significant water source for shallow-rooted plants, and daily transformation of gypsum to anhydrite
572 (CaSO_4) (G→A) and nightly transformation of anhydrite to gypsum (A→G) was suggested.
573 However, the changes in soil water content and isotopic composition of water along soil profiles, as
574 well as the $\delta^2\text{H}$ – $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ biplots with gypseous free soil water and xylem sap isotopic compositions as a
575 results of G→A and A→G transformation, could be interpreted in a completely different way.

576 Kasprzyk and Jasińska (1998) showed that the isotopic composition of gypsum crystallization water
577 reflects that of the mother brine. Recrystallization of gypsum or diffusion of water into intact crystals
578 during diagenesis might lead to important variations in isotopic ratios of hydrogen and oxygen.
579 Finally, evolution of the isotopic composition of crystallization water might include evaporation,
580 hydration and isotopic exchange. Another important question is whether specific isotopic
581 fractionation of hydrogen and oxygen may occur in xylem sap of plants or in plants roots. Zhao et al.,
582 (2016) concluded that remarkable $\delta^2\text{H}$ differences between xylem sap and twig water, root water and
583 core water provided direct evidence that deuterium fractionation occurred between xylem sap and
584 root or stem tissue water. Moreover, Barbeta et al. (2019) and Poca et al. (2019) showed the existence
585 of isotopic fractionation processes either in the soil-root interface or within plant woody tissues.
586 These studies indicate that deuterium fractionation could be a common phenomenon in drylands and
587 not G→A and A→G transformations as suggested by Palacio et al. (2014) and de la Puente et al.
588 (2022).

589 While the above-discussed studies deal with soil water uptake by plants, microbiologically
590 induced changes of the hydration state of Ca-sulfate were recently suggested by Huang et al. (2020).
591 These authors described a supposed mechanism of water extraction from gypsum by cyanobacteria
592 (*Chroococcidiopsis* sp.) sampled from endolithic microbial communities inhabiting gypsum
593 substrates in the Atacama Desert, and cultivated in the laboratory. They claimed that the
594 microorganisms can extract crystallization water (i.e., structurally ordered water) from the gypsum,
595 inducing a phase transformation from gypsum to anhydrite (G→A) occurring under “dry
596 conditions” in the contact zone between a “dry biofilm” and the gypsum substrate. This work has a
597 number of major conceptual problems (Wierzchos et al., 2020a). First, Huang et al. (2020) showed
598 the presence of gypsum and/or anhydrite in the inoculated samples using only X-ray diffraction
599 analysis and partially by Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy techniques, where both gypsum and
600 anhydrite phases already existed before the experiment with the cyanobacteria was started.
601 Consequently, the presence of anhydrite within these samples was expected, and was not necessarily
602 due to water extraction by the microorganisms. Moreover, the G→A transformation requires
603 conditions such as the presence of 1.5 M H_2SO_4 (pH = 0.18) and a temperature of 80°C or higher
604 (according to the citation in Huang et al., 2020). These theoretical conditions were not met in the
605 described experiments, and cannot be achieved within the biofilm. Any dissociation and liberation of
606 H^+ is only possible in liquid water and not under “dry conditions” as suggested by Huang et al.
607 (2020). Furthermore, the interpretation of the results by Huang et al. (2020) was inconsistent with
608 previous reports which demonstrated absence of the transformation of gypsum to anhydrite (G→A)
609 *in situ* in natural endolithic microhabitats in the Atacama Desert (DiRuggiero et al., 2013; Wierzchos
610 et al., 2011; Vitek et al., 2013; Wierzchos et al., 2015; Vitek et al., 2016; Meslier et al., 2018). Vitek
611 et al. (2016) discussed the thermodynamic impossibility of the G→A transformation under the
612 polyextreme environmental conditions of the Atacama Desert, and this was supported by the Raman
613 imaging dataset of the host rock and the hydration state of Ca-sulfate: gypsum and not anhydrite or
614 bassanite was present in the contact zone of the cyanobacteria. Moreover, in a new study (Huang et
615 al., 2022), no anhydrite phase as a result of supposed G→A transformation was detected below a
616 cyanobacteria biofilm in a similar experiment, using similar material and the same methodology as
617 used by Huang et al. (2020). Likewise, recently, Douchi et al. (2023) repeated the experiment by
618 Huang et al. (2020) using the same *Chroococcidiopsis* strain isolated from the Atacama’s gypsum
619 rock and *Synechocystis* collected from the Negev Desert (Israel). No evidence was found that these
620 cyanobacteria are capable of extracting water from the gypsum, even after 15 days of dehydration.

621

622 4.4 Microbial communities associated with subaquatic crystalline gypsum

623 Gypsum is deposited on the bottom of evaporation ponds of intermediate salinity (120-250 g l⁻¹). The
624 gypsum crystals are often arranged such that light penetrates deep into the crust, and photosynthesis
625 can occur down to depths of several centimeters (Caumette et al., 1994; Oren et al., 1995; Oren 2009;
626 Figure 2D). Salt-tolerant oxygenic photosynthetic microorganisms (mainly cyanobacteria, sometimes
627 accompanied by diatoms and other eukaryotic algae) often colonize the gypsum layer.

628 Dissimilatory sulfate reduction in the deeper anaerobic layers generates sulfide that diffuses upward
629 and reaches parts of the gypsum crust where light is still available. This enables development of
630 sulfide oxidizing anoxygenic phototrophic bacteria. Many members of the genera *Chromatium* or
631 *Halochromatium*, *Thiocapsa*, *Ectothiorhodospira*, *Halorhodospira*, and related photosynthetic sulfur
632 bacteria are markedly halophilic or salt-tolerant (Caumette et al., 1994).

633 The presence of layered communities of oxygenic and anoxygenic phototrophs in benthic gypsum
634 crusts has been documented from salterns on the Mediterranean coast of Spain (Cornée 1984; Ortí
635 Cabo et al., 1984; Thomas, 1984; Villanueva et al., 1994) and France (Thomas and Geisler 1982;
636 Cornee, 1982; Cornée, 1984; Cornee, 1989; Caumette, 1993; Caumette et al., 1994), the Red Sea
637 coast of Israel (Oren, 1997; Oren et al., 1995; Canfield et al., 2004; Sørensen et al., 2004; Sørensen et
638 al., 2005; Ionescu et al., 2007) and Saudi Arabia (Aref et al., 2020), an inland saltern in Egypt (Taher,
639 2014), and sabkhas and salterns at Guerrero Negro, Mexico (Vogel et al., 2009; Vogel et al., 2010).
640 Many studies were devoted to the gypsum crust developing in the salterns of Eilat, Israel (Oren et al.,
641 2009) (Figure 2D). The upper layer is generally colored yellow-orange-brown due to the presence of
642 unicellular cyanobacteria. Because of the high *in situ* light intensity, the cells contain little
643 chlorophyll and accessory photosynthetic pigments such as phycocyanin and other phycobiliproteins,
644 but massive amounts of carotenoid pigments such as myxoxanthophyll and echinenone are
645 accumulated to protect the cells against high radiation levels (Villanueva et al., 1994; Oren et al.,
646 1995). They were assigned to the genera *Eubhalothece*, *Aphanothece*, or *Cyanothece* in different
647 publications. Copious amounts of polysaccharide slime are generally produced by these
648 cyanobacteria.

649 Large concentrations of mycosporine-like amino acids (MAAs) were found in the community of
650 orange unicellular cyanobacteria in the benthic gypsum crust of the Eilat salterns. Two MAAs were
651 detected, one with an absorption maximum at 331-332 nm, and one at 362 nm (Oren, 1997). The
652 intracellular concentration of MAAs in the cyanobacterial cells were estimated to be at least 100 mM,
653 representing >3% of the cells' wet weight, which probably is the highest MAA concentration ever
654 reported (Oren, 1997). The two compounds were identified as mycosporine-2-glycine (Kedar et al.,
655 2002) and a novel compound with the maximum absorbance at 362 nm identified as 2-(E)-3-(E)-2,3-
656 dihydroxyprop-1-enylimino-mycosporine-alanine (Volkman et al., 2006). These MAAs may also
657 contribute to osmotic regulation of the cells. When the salinity of the medium was reduced by
658 dilution with fresh water, the MAAs were rapidly excreted to the medium in amounts proportional to
659 the degree of dilution (Oren, 1997). The main osmotic stabilizer of these microbial communities was
660 identified as glycine betaine (Oren et al., 2013).

661 Below the orange layer, a layer of filamentous dark-green cyanobacteria is generally found. Here the
662 available light intensities are much lower, and therefore the cells increase their light harvesting ability
663 by accumulating chlorophyll *a* and the blue pigment phycocyanin. The straight filaments
664 characteristically found in this layer were tentatively identified as *Phormidium*, *Lyngbya*, or
665 *Oscillatoria* by different authors. They are sometimes accompanied by tight spirals of *Halospirulina*
666 (*Spirulina subsalsa*) (Oren et al., 1995).

667 A microelectrode study showed that the green cyanobacteria layer in the Eilat gypsum crust is
668 exposed to dramatic diel changes: from anaerobic conditions with sulfide accumulating during the
669 night to oxygen supersaturation at noon (Canfield et al., 2004). The filamentous cyanobacteria are
670 well adapted to such changes. In addition to oxygenic photosynthesis with water as the electron
671 donor, they can use sulfide as the electron donor in an anoxygenic type of photosynthesis driven by
672 Photosystem I without participation of Photosystem II (Oren et al., 2005; Ionescu et al., 2007; Oren
673 et al., 2009). The ability to lead a partially anaerobic life is also reflected in the fatty acid
674 composition of these cyanobacteria. Lipids of filamentous cyanobacteria generally contain
675 polyunsaturated fatty acids, whose biosynthesis is oxygen-dependent. In contrast, the layer of
676 *Phormidium*-like green filaments was virtually devoid of polyunsaturated fatty acids. The content of
677 monounsaturated fatty acids was dominated by 16:1 cis 7 and 18:1 cis 9. The positions of the double
678 bonds suggest that the biosynthesis of these unsaturated fatty acids may proceed by an oxygen-
679 independent pathway in which an intermediate β -hydroxyalkanoyl-ACP is dehydrated, rather than the
680 oxygen-dependent desaturation of the corresponding saturated fatty acid (Oren et al., 2005; Ionescu
681 et al., 2007; Oren et al., 2009).

682 When enough light penetrates below the green layers to reach the anaerobic sulfide-containing area, a
683 purple layer of anoxygenic photosynthetic sulfur bacteria develops. Their red-purple color is mainly
684 due to spirilloxanthin and other carotenoids. Bacteriochlorophyll *a* is the photosynthetically active
685 pigment. Its *in situ* long-wavelength absorption maximum is in the infrared range (800–860 nm),
686 enabling the cells to use wavelengths that are not absorbed by the orange and green communities
687 above (Oren et al., 1995).

688 The phototrophic populations are accompanied by diverse communities of microorganisms including
689 aerobic heterotrophic bacteria, protists, chemoautotrophic sulfur oxidizers, anaerobic fermentative
690 bacteria, dissimilatory sulfate reducers, and methanogens.

691 Similar gypsum accumulations with layered pigmented microbial communities were documented
692 from saltworks in the Dhabhan area on the Red Sea coast of Saudi Arabia (Aref et al., 2020). Planar
693 wavy gypsum microbialites were found at relatively low salinities. Individual and coalesced dome-
694 shaped stromatolites of 30–70 cm in diameter and 20–30 cm in height were present at higher
695 salinities. Similar gypsum domes with lithifying brown, green, red, and black-layered microbial mats
696 were observed from the inland saltworks in the Fayum depression, Egypt. The green community
697 contained both straight (*Oscillatoria/Phormidium* type) and coiled (*Halospirulina*-type) filamentous
698 cyanobacteria (Taher 2014). Subaqueous gypsum deposits with stratified, pigmented microbial
699 communities were reported from the sabkhas and salterns of Guerrero Negro, Mexico. These deposits
700 ranged from meter-thick crusts forming in saltern concentration ponds to columnar microbial mats
701 with internally crystallized gypsum granules developing in natural anchialine pools. Here gypsum
702 granules precipitated in the extracellular polymeric substance matrix. The biofilms appeared to
703 influence the dissolution and granularization of precipitation surfaces, formation of gypsum crystals
704 with equant and distorted habits, and precipitation of trace carbonate and oxide phases (Vogel et al.,
705 2009; Vogel et al., 2010).

706 Microbial community dynamics within benthic gypsum crusts of evaporation ponds were analyzed in
707 the salterns of Salins-de-Giraud (Camargue, France) (Caumette 1993; Caumette et al., 1994), and
708 Eilat, Israel (Canfield et al., 2004). Techniques employed included use of oxygen and sulfide
709 microelectrodes, measurement of sulfate reduction using radioisotopes, and measurements of
710 methane evolution. At both sites, oxygen and sulfide were largely recycled within the crusts. In the
711 Salins-de-Giraud gypsum, oxygen production rates up to $2 \mu\text{mol cm}^{-3} \text{h}^{-1}$ were measured during the
712 maximum daylight, and sulfate reduction rates (average $8.2 \mu\text{mol cm}^{-3} \text{day}^{-1}$) were among the
713 highest reported in the literature. Sulfide oxidation in the gypsum crust when exposed to light was

714 calculated to be $12.7 \mu\text{mol cm}^{-3} \text{h}^{-1}$. It was estimated that 65-95% of the diel sulfide production was
715 reoxidized within the crust. Sulfide oxidation can be mainly attributed to phototrophic purple sulfur
716 bacteria, including *Chromatium salexigens* and *Thiocapsa halophila*, isolated from this site. Both can
717 grow at the low light intensities that reach the purple layer in the crust. Accumulated sulfide can be
718 oxidized abiotically by oxygen produced by sulfide-tolerant cyanobacteria above the purple layer
719 (Caumette 1993, Caumette et al., 1994). Cyanobacteria may also be actively involved in sulfide
720 reoxidation by performing anoxygenic photosynthesis (Oren et al., 2005; Oren et al., 2009). Diel
721 measurements of the distribution and dynamics of oxygen and sulfide within the Eilat gypsum crust
722 showed that only 16-34% of the oxygen produced in the crust escaped; the remainder was internally
723 recycled. (Canfield et al., 2004).

724

725 In experiments in which gypsum crusts from the Eilat salterns and of slurries prepared from them
726 were exposed to changes in salinity, the unicellular and filamentous cyanobacteria metabolized at
727 near-optimum rates at the *in situ* salinity of 215 g l^{-1} ; however, the anoxygenic phototrophs preferred
728 salinities between 100 and 120 g l^{-1} (Sørensen et al., 2004). The purple sulfur bacteria *Chromatium*
729 *salexigens* and *Thiocapsa halophila* isolated from the Salins-de-Giraud crust grew optimally at 60 -
730 100 g l^{-1} NaCl, and had their maximal salt tolerance at 200 g l^{-1} NaCl, close to the *in situ* salinity
731 (Caumette, 1993). Sulfate reduction by the Eilat sediment slurries was optimal at 100 - 120 g l^{-1} salt; at
732 the *in situ* salinity, activity was strongly inhibited. Methanogens were better adapted to the *in situ*
733 salinity, but they contributed little to the anaerobic mineralization. In slurries with a salinity of 180 g
734 l^{-1} or less, methanogens were inhibited by increased activity of sulfate-reducing bacteria competing
735 for the same substrates (Sørensen et al., 2004).

736

737 Understanding the distribution and mode of survival of different halophiles in bottom gypsum layers
738 is deeply achieved in few subaquatic sites, mostly salterns. Comparing the situation with other sites
739 of differing water and microbial community composition would let us understand the role of
740 changing physico-chemical conditions on microbial colonizations.

741

742 In summary, many different approaches have been used to study the microbial communities
743 associated with subaquatic crystalline gypsum, yielding qualitative and quantitative information on
744 the types of microorganisms present, using phylogenetic analyses, chemotaxonomic markers,
745 cultivation-dependent methods, as well as *in situ* activity measurements. Ideally, all methodologies
746 should be applied at the same time to obtain a comprehensive picture of the impact of the
747 microorganisms on the ecosystem. The interdisciplinary study of the Eilat salterns performed in April
748 2008 by an international team of experts shows that this can be achieved (Prášil et al., 2009;
749 Řeháková et al., 2009; Sørensen et al., 2009; Woelfel et al., 2009). More such studies in different
750 gypsum ecosystems worldwide should be encouraged.

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756 5. Fossil biomarkers in gypsum

757 Organic matter is not only present in gypsum that was colonized recently or subrecently but can also
758 be incorporated as much older remnant. Authigenic fossilized organic matter in sedimentary gypsum
759 represents carbonaceous residues of previously existing microorganisms and their degradation
760 products sealed inside crystalline gypsum. Remnants of microbial life and biomarkers were also
761 described sealed in halite (Isaji et al., 2019). Thus, pigmented bacteria were observed in halite from
762 evaporitic series 9 ka to 1.44 Ma old in Death Valley, Saline Valley and Searles Lake, USA (Winters
763 et al., 2013).

764 Unlike fine-grain gypsum or limestones, crystalline gypsum rarely encloses remnants of authigenic
765 fossilized organic matter. When observing gypsum crystals with the naked eye or with an optical
766 microscope, dark μm to mm-large aggregates can occasionally be found inside transparent tabular
767 selenitic crystals. This is especially well known for Messinian age gypsum from Italian sites, for
768 instance from Banengo, Monticino, Moncucco, Polenzo and Govone in the Piedmont Basin (Dela
769 Pierre et al., 2015; Pellegrino et al., 2021; Carnevale et al., 2019; Natalicchio et al., 2021; Sabino et
770 al., 2020), from Vena del Gesso and Monte Tondo in the north eastern Apennines (Vai and Ricci
771 Lucchi, 1977; Natalicchio et al., 2021), and from Spanish Perales in the Sorbas basin (Pellegrino et
772 al., 2021). Obtaining more information on such fossilized organic matter in crystalline gypsum, using
773 microscopy techniques and complementary organic geochemical studies, is of highest importance for
774 sedimentological reconstructions in such evaporitic sedimentary basins to elucidate the evolution of
775 the Mediterranean in the Mid- and Late Miocene and during the Messinian salinity crisis (Natalicchio
776 et al., 2021; Sabino et al., 2021; Andreeto et al., 2021).

777 The origin of blackish and brownish aggregates in transparent gypsum crystals can be mineral or
778 organic in nature. Clays are commonly found more or less dispersed as cloudy components in
779 crystals. However, more detailed examination using optical microscopy allows to distinguish
780 structures due to organic remnants. Vai and Ricci Lucchi (1977) described fossilised remains of algal
781 origin in two types of gypsum in the Vena del Gesso Basin (Italy), while massive transparent
782 crystalline selenite from Borgo Tossignano contains turbid cores consisting of algal tubules.
783 Stromatolitic gypsum from the same area consisting of crystalline selenite encloses micritic algal
784 laminae, supporting the interpretation of this facies as algal mats. Panieri et al. (2008), Lugli et al.,
785 (2010) described microbial communities from the Vena del Gesso area, including the massive,
786 bending and branching selenite from the Monte Tondo quarry. Different types of filamentous
787 microorganisms were found, suggesting coexistence of different taxonomic groups in the original
788 marine environment.

789 Using advanced visualisation techniques (CLSM), several types of fossilised structures were
790 observed in Vena del Gesso (Monte Tondo quarry) selenites. In the bottom nucleated gypsum both
791 broad filamentous fossils and smaller-diameter filaments were found (Schopf et al., 2012).
792 Filamentous fossils were also described from gypsum crystals from Banengo (Messinian, NW Italy)
793 by Della Pierre et al. (2015). These authors questioned the previous interpretation of similar
794 structures in gypsum by Vai and Ricci Lucchi (1977) as benthic algae. Instead, they suggested that
795 the observed remnants are sulfide-oxidizing bacteria, based on morphological comparison of the
796 fossilized matter with colorless filaments of *Beggiatoa* or *Thioploca*, and due to the presence of
797 polysulfide in the investigated material.

798 Silicified, well-preserved diatoms were found in selenitic gypsum from Vena del Gesso (Monte
799 Tondo quarry) and Banengo (Piedmont basin). Diatoms similar to members of the modern genus
800 *Navicula* were found in bottom-nucleated gypsum of the Vena del Gesso Formation, as well as
801 permineralized unicells, similar to the extant chroococcacean cyanobacterium *Gloeocapsa* (Schopf et

802 al., 2012). In the Banengo zone, the diatoms appear intermingled with brownish-greenish organic
803 remains and filamentous microfossils attributed to remains of sulfide-oxidizing bacteria. The most
804 common types resemble *Chaetoceros* sp. and *Biddulphia* sp. frustules (Carnevale et al., 2019).

805 Messinian gypsum sites with selenitic and resedimented gypsum in Calabria were investigated by
806 Costanzo et al. (2019) and Cipriani et al. (2021). In Benestare (Ionian forearc basin, La Cattolica
807 formation), rounded-grain aggregate gypsum and branching-like facies contain resedimented gypsum
808 containing brown, black, and reddish organic matter in gypsum inclusions or aggregates. The
809 gypsum and especially the swallowtail twins contained inclusions and rich aggregates of dark organic
810 matter, sometimes showing blue or green fluorescence.

811 Raman spectra of dark and blackish carbonaceous material dispersed in transparent selenitic gypsum
812 were reported from Monte Tondo quarry, near Borgo Rivola, Messinian Vena del Gesso (Schopf et
813 al., 2012), from Banengo (Piedmont Basin, Italy) (Dela Pierre et al., 2015), and from Perales (Spain)
814 (Pellegrino et al., 2021). Commonly, diagnostic Raman spectroscopic features corresponding to
815 pigments or other biomarkers were lost due to diagenetic evolution.

816 However, detailed analysis of biomarkers within fossil organic aggregates or dispersed compounds
817 from gypsum is possible using other modern organic geochemical tools (Sinninghe Damsté et al.,
818 2002; Turich et al., 2007; Turich and Freeman, 2011). The Soxhlet-extracted hydrocarbon fraction
819 found in gypsum and marls originating from the Perticara basin (Romagna Marche Messinian
820 evaporitic basin) was dominated by n-C22, pristane and phytane and by characteristic assemblages of
821 pregnanes, homopregnanes and norcholestanes, norhopane, hopane and possibly gammacerane. These
822 compounds are interpreted as originating from photosynthetic prokaryotes such as cyanobacteria
823 from hypersaline environments (ten Haven et al., 1985). Based on subsequent studies from Vena del
824 Gesso, Sinninghe Damsté et al. (1995) suggested, that gammacerane is derived from anaerobic
825 bacterivorous ciliates. The distribution of biomarkers was studied in a series of extracts from freshly
826 drilled material of evaporites sampled in Mediterranean Deep Sea Drilling Project cores. Investigated
827 gypsum and anhydrite samples contained abundant remains of lipids derived from cell membranes of
828 archaea: abundant amounts of glycerol dialkyl glycerol tetraethers (GDGTs), including acyclic
829 caldarchaeol (GDGT-0) and cyclic crenarchaeol (GDGT-5), as well as archaeol diethers (Christeleit
830 et al., 2015). A recent geochemical study focused on biomarkers obtained from gypsum sampled
831 from marginal basins across the Mediterranean (Nijar, Spain; Vena del Gesso, Italy; Heraklion,
832 Crete; and Psematismenos, Cyprus) (Natalicchio et al., 2022). The excellent preservation of
833 molecular fossils and the determination of compound-specific carbon stable isotope compositions
834 enabled the recognition of the main groups of microorganisms inhabiting Messinian aquatic
835 ecosystems at the time the gypsum was deposited. The molecular fossil assemblages of gypsum from
836 different Mediterranean basins investigated differ from modern marine gypsum deposits forming in
837 shallow-water hypersaline settings. The abundance of lipids of planktic halophilic archaea, planktic
838 thaumarchaeota, and a community of benthic archaea identified allowed Natalicchio et al. (2022) to
839 suggest alternating conditions in the sedimentary basin where sulfide reducing bacteria played role in
840 the formation of chemotrophic microbial mats. Similarly, in another geological setting (Oxford Clay
841 Formation, Callowian, Jura) a complex combination of fossil record data with biomarker content
842 (e.g. isorenieratane) in black shales allowed advanced reconstruction of bottom-water oxygenation
843 level and the estimation of oxic-dioxic events (Kenig et al. 2004).

844 Stromatolites can also be built by gypsum, and some examples include traces of organic matter or
845 mineralized remnants. Examples of Messinian gypsum stromatolites were investigated in Sicily
846 (Schreiber et al., 1976) and western Cyprus (Rouchy and Monty 1981; Rouchy and Monty 2000).
847 Gypsum stromatolites at the Polemi section (western Cyprus) contain characteristic sedimentary
848 structures, and organic remnants are common as filaments dispersed in the laminae (Rouchy and

849 Monty, 2000). The authors suggested that these remnants are of cyanobacterial origin, contrasting to
850 those formed by fecal pellets of the brine shrimp *Artemia*, suggested by Schreiber et al., (1976) to be
851 of relevance in Sicilian Messinian gypsum. Allwood et al., (2013) reported biosignatures in columnar
852 stromatolites from fine-grained gypsum from the same section (Polemi), and also documented
853 microbially laminated selenites from the Kalavassos Psematismenos basin (southern Cyprus).

854

855 **Overviewed studies show excellent achievements of modern analytical tools for studying traces of**
856 **microbes inside gypsum. The occurrence of such chemical or even morphological remnants would be**
857 **investigated in depth even more, in additional, well characterized gypsum crystals or masses from**
858 **sites of different age. Are up to now described traces typical only in Messinian age gypsum from the**
859 **Mediterranean ? More could be understood investigating gypsum of Permian and Triassic age for**
860 **instance from Harz or Alpine areas.**

861

862 **6. Gypsum endoliths and astrobiology**

863 **How about to discover similar type of microbial colonizations of gypsum on Mars? Parnell et al.**
864 **(2004); Edwards et al. (2005a) ;Edwards et al. (2005b), for instance, showed detecting pigments as**
865 **biomarkers in gypsum using Raman spectroscopy . They hypothesized about future possibilities of**
866 **detecting similar biomarkers also in gypsum on Mars. Recently, astrobiological projects focus on the**
867 **Martian subsurface to exploit properties of the rocky matrices and evaluate their properties to**
868 **preserve biomarkers (Bhartia et al., 2021; Farley et al., 2020).**

869 Large deposits of evaporitic minerals on Mars were observed by both orbit-based measurements
870 (e.g., Christensen et al., 2008; Osterloo et al., 2008) and by *in situ* analyses by robotic missions (e.g.,
871 Squyres et al., 2004; Grotzinger et al., 2005; Scheller et al., 2022). Sulfate minerals have been
872 identified in outcrops as well as regolith on Mars, as extensively demonstrated by measurements
873 obtained by the Mars Exploration Rover missions Spirit and Opportunity (e.g. McLennan et al.,
874 2005). Contrary to common Earth scenarios, sulfates largely dominate over chloride salts in Meridiani
875 Planum, the landing site of the Opportunity rover. This is interpreted to be related to acidic
876 weathering of basaltic rocks and the sulfur-rich Martian lithosphere with a high SO₃/Cl ratio in
877 volatiles (Clark and Baird, 1979; Clark et al., 2005). Fishbaugh et al., (2006) suggested that the north
878 polar gypsum area of Mars was formed as an evaporitic deposit. Data from excavated regolith
879 indicated presence of a high portion of Mg-sulfates with minor amounts of Ca- and Fe-sulfates
880 (Wang et al., 2006). Gypsum veins cutting sedimentary sequences were reported in Endeavour
881 Crater (Squyres et al., 2012) and in Gale crater (Nachon et al., 2014). The latter authors underlined
882 the importance of gypsum in astrobiology. Gale crater sediments contain in their lacustrine
883 sedimentary rocks also remarkable lenticular features (roughly 1-2 mm long). With no signs of
884 sulfate minerals they are interpreted as morphological pseudomorphs, remnants
885 after gypsum accumulated previously in the past (Kah et al., 2018).

886 Deposition of evaporitic sulfates may thus have been widespread on Early Mars. Rapin et al. (2019)
887 used data obtained during the Curiosity rover exploration of Gale crater to show the presence of
888 important sulfate enrichment in the sedimentary sequences. It may have originated through
889 evaporative processes during a saline interval following climatic change to a more arid environment.
890 Gypsum rocks are therefore excellent candidates for future search of biomarkers on Mars (Edwards
891 et al., 2005a; Bowden and Parnell 2007).

892 The Perseverance rover (Mars 2020 mission, NASA) includes different tools for evaluation of the
893 mineral composition and detecting biomarkers in rocks (Farley et al., 2020). Raman spectrometers
894 equipped with excitation lasers of 532 nm (SuperCam) and 248.6 nm (Mission) are now operating on
895 the Martian surface as part of the Scanning Habitable Environments with Raman and Luminescence
896 for Organics and Chemicals (SHERLOC) (Bhartia et al., 2021). A future Exomars European mission
897 to Mars with the Rosalind Franklin rover will also allow detecting biomarkers using several tools,
898 including a Raman spectrometer (Rull et al., 2017). Samples of rocky material will be drilled from a
899 depth of around 2 m. The current Mars missions do not focus on sulfates, but they employ Raman
900 systems to search for traces of possible biomarkers in different rocks.

901 In the last twenty years Raman spectroscopy was shown to be a suitable tool to detect biomarkers in
902 rocky matrices, including gypsum. It has been demonstrated that under laboratory conditions,
903 carotenoids, commonly associated with microbial colonization, may be detected in gypsum substrates
904 at relatively low concentrations (Vítek et al., 2009). Measurements were performed using laboratory-
905 based (Osterrothová and Jehlička, 2011) as well as miniaturized portable instruments (Culka et al.,
906 2012). The limit of detection by miniaturized Raman instrumentation for β -carotene was 0.1 ppm,
907 while for carbonaceous matter (graphite, shungite) dispersed in gypsum the detection limit was 0.1%,
908 showing the high sensitivity of Raman instrumentation to detect the conjugated polyene structure of
909 carotenoids (Vítek et al., 2014). Demaret et al. (2020) further studied the detection of solid
910 dispersions of β -carotene and L-cysteine in gypsum, using Raman spectroscopy. The ability of
911 miniaturized Raman instruments, including prototypes of Martian Raman spectrometers, to detect
912 photosynthetic and protective pigments in gypsum and other evaporitic minerals has been evaluated
913 under different conditions (Vítek et al., 2014; Jehlička and Oren 2013; Culka et al., 2014; Malherbe
914 et al., 2017).

915 Recently, molecular biomarkers were successfully detected along a vertical profile down to 80 cm in
916 evaporitic sediments from the hyperarid core of the Atacama Desert during the NASA Atacama
917 Rover Astrobiology Drilling Studies (ARADS) Mars drilling simulation campaign (Moreno-Paz et
918 al., 2023). The authors described changes in the bacterial community and metabolisms with depth
919 within the profile of playa sediments. The measurements were undertaken remotely and
920 autonomously using antibody microarray-based Life Detector Chip (for further information and
921 details see Glass et al., 2023, Moreno-Paz et al., 2023).

922 Several terrestrial sites rich in gypsum with microbial colonizations worldwide were proposed as
923 Mars analog areas and recommended for testing approaches and instrumentation before deploying
924 such tools on Mars (Harris et al., 2022; Shen et al., 2022). Suggested Mars analogs include the Chott
925 el Gharsa sabkha in Tunisia (Barbieri et al., 2006), gypsum mounds in Tunisia (Stivaletta and
926 Barbieri, 2009), the Atacama Desert (Wierzchos et al., 2011), and the Sorbas area in SE Spain
927 (Martinez-Frias et al., 2006). Fairén et al. (2010) reviewed the current knowledge of a selection of
928 Mars analogues on Earth, including gypsum containing environments and grouped them in their
929 relevance with respect to climatic stages of the Martian geological history. To evaluate the possible
930 preservation of microbial lipids under Mars analog conditions, Cheng et al. (2017) conducted a
931 mineralogical and organic geochemistry study on evaporitic samples collected from the Dalangtan
932 Playa, northwestern Qaidam Basin, China. Further studies of such Mars evaporitic analogue sites are
933 currently being organized to test novel analytical approaches and strategies for future space missions.

934

935 **Finally, it can be understood that gypsum sites worldwide can be seen as training fields not only for**
936 **geobiology or microbiology but also for future astrobiological studies. One area is direct onsite**
937 **terrestrial deployment and testing of dedicated instrumentation to be suggested for next astrobiology-**

938 focused missions to allow detecting biomarkers in gypsum. On the basis of obtained experience,
939 another step is additional methodic development and technological enhancement and preparing
940 possible rover missions on Mars rocky gypsum . Clearly, there, mostly subsurface portions of
941 gypsum would be of highest relevance for search of extinct or extant Life.

942

943 **7. Conclusions and perspectives**

944 Gypsum commonly hosts a variety of microorganisms. Numerous sites with colonized gypsum have
945 been discovered worldwide. Gypsum is often colonized by endolithic microbial communities that
946 develop within pores beneath the rock surface (cryptoendolithic habitats), in cracks or in flat spaces
947 in the frame of rock cleavage (chasmoendolithic habitats), within pores at the bottom part of the rock
948 (hypoendolithic habitats). Endolithic microbial communities were documented from environments
949 that differ greatly in water availability and temperature, from saline and hypersaline lakes and ponds
950 where gypsum precipitates to the hyperarid areas of the Atacama Desert and other hot and arid
951 environments, as well as Antarctic and Arctic zones.

952 What are the main gaps in our knowledge of microbial colonizations of gypsum? We still need a
953 better understanding of the mode of microbial colonization in gypsum compared to those in other
954 minerals – carbonates, quartz, granites, or even volcanic rocks. We need to understand how the
955 characteristics of the mineral environment influence the survival and growth of microorganisms in
956 rocks. Clearly, for phototrophic microorganisms, life within gypsum may be advantageous as the
957 mineral protects the cells against excessive insolation and ultraviolet radiation, while allowing
958 sufficient photosynthetically active radiation to reach the cells.

959 **Are there substantial differences between microbial colonization of gypsum and in/on carbonates ?**
960 **What are the properties of calcite or dolomite which would limit the development endolithic**
961 **colonization in these sedimentary matrices commonly occurring as outcrops? Additionnaly, would**
962 **epilithic microbial growth be possible on the surface of such minerals falling together with gypsum**
963 **and halite in the group of highly soluble minerals.**

964 For a better understanding of water origin and its sources in gypsum layers or aggregates it is essential
965 to evaluate the global distribution of gypsum colonizations under different climatic conditions, in
966 sites of restricted water access as well as milder and wet environments, in lowlands as well as at high
967 altitudes. Where do gypsum colonizations occur at high altitudes (in addition to the well-investigated
968 Atacama Desert) and in extremely wet tropical areas? What are the limitations to colonization of
969 gypsum under high altitude mountain non-arid conditions? How do the low stability and enhanced
970 weathering and dissolution under high rain and snow input affect superficial gypsum colonization?
971 To what extent is colonization limited by environmental parameters such as high UV radiation and
972 low temperature? To what extent do protective pigments allow survival of gypsum endolithic
973 communities under high altitude, high UV and high humidity and water/snow conditions? What can
974 we learn from the application of metagenomics and metatranscriptomics about the structure and
975 activity of the communities? Metagenomic studies were few (Casero et al., 2020; Schultze-Makuch et
976 al., 2021; see Table 3) and we are not aware of any metatranscriptomic studies in gypsum crust
977 communities. To what extent may gypsum microbial colonizations be a result of a global distribution
978 in accordance with the proposed global metacommunity hypothesis (Walker and Pace, 2007).

979 What is the sequence of steps during the transformation of gypsum crystals to a more or less porous
980 matrix that allows microorganisms to enter its spaces? How is microbial colonization of gypsum

981 initiated? How common do such colonizations occur in neofomed and recrystalised gypsum in
982 karstic areas? Such knowledge needs also to be acquired to obtain a more complete understanding of
983 the effects of biota on the rocks and their transformations. The connection between the inorganic
984 phase of the matrix and biotic phenomena also needs to be clarified.

985 In spite of claims made in the past, there is no convincing evidence to support the hypothesis that the
986 crystallization water of gypsum may be available to the microbial communities in endoliths in
987 hyperarid environments.

988 The geological record shows extensive evidence for residues of microbes in gypsum derived from
989 Tertiary seas. Our ability to detect living endolithic microbial communities in gypsum and fossilized
990 communities in buried gypsum deposits or their biomarkers can be used as the basis for the search for
991 such communities in gypsum on Mars and possibly elsewhere in the universe. The search for life
992 beyond Earth represents a major challenge for the 21st century. Current and forthcoming projects by
993 NASA and ESA (Mars 2020 and Exomars 2020) include robotic rovers to better investigate Martian
994 rocky outcrops or subsurface rocks through a combination of imaging and spectroscopic techniques.
995 Analytical approaches for biomarker tracing include spectroscopic tools enabling the collection of
996 spectra (e.g. Raman spectra) on-site or even remotely. Endolithic communities on Earth are useful
997 model systems to test and further develop instruments to be sent to sites beyond Earth. Further
998 deployment of dedicated miniaturized instrumentation under different extreme climatic conditions on
999 Earth is essential to prepare for successful applications on Mars. If it will be possible to return
1000 Martian rocky samples to Earth in sealed containers, the experience gained during the application of
1001 modern lab-based tools to detect traces of biomarkers in gypsum endoliths will be important to assess
1002 the possible presence of traces of present or past life on Mars.

1003

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1006

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- 1021 Allwood, A.C., Burch, I.W., Rouchy, J.M., Coleman M. (2013). Morphological biosignatures in
1022 gypsum: diverse formation processes of Messinian (similar to 6.0 Ma) gypsum stromatolites.
1023 *Astrobiology* 13, 870–86. doi: 10.1089/ast.2013.1021
- 1024 Andreetto, F., Aloisi, G., Raad, F., Heida, H., Flecker, R.M., Agiadi, K., et al. (2021). Freshening of
1025 the Mediterranean Salt Giant: controversies and certainties around the terminal (Upper Gypsum
1026 and Lago-Mare) phases of the Messinian Salinity Crisis. *Earth. Sci. Rev.* 216, 103577. doi:
1027 10.1016/j.earscirev.2021.103577
- 1028 Aref, M.A., Mahmoud, A. and Taj, R.J. (2018). Recent evaporite deposition associated with
1029 microbial mats, Al-Kharrar supratidal-intertidal sabkha, Rabigh area, Red Sea coastal plain of
1030 Saudi Arabia. *Facies* 64, 28. doi: 10.1007/s10347-018-0539-y
- 1031 Aref, M.A., Taj R.J., and Mannaa, A.A. (2020). Sedimentological implications of microbial mats,
1032 gypsum, and halite in Dhahban solar saltwork, Red Sea coast, Saudi Arabia. *Facies* 66, 10. doi:
1033 10.1007/s10347-020-0594-z
- 1034 Auvray, C., Homand, F., and Sorgi, C. (2004). The aging of gypsum in underground mines. *Eng.*
1035 *Geol.* 74, 183–96. doi: 10.1016/j.enggeo.2004.03.008
- 1036 Babel, M. (2004). Models for evaporite, selenite and gypsum microbialite deposition in ancient saline
1037 basins. *Acta. Geol. Polon.* 54, 291–249.
- 1038 Barbeta, A., Jones, S.P., Clavé, L., Gimeno, T.E., Fréjaville, B., Wohl, S., et al. (2019). Unexplained
1039 hydrogen isotope offsets complicate the identification and quantification of tree water sources in
1040 a riparian forest. *Hydrol. Earth System Sci.* 23, 1–31. doi: 10.5194/hess-23-2129-2019
- 1041 Barbieri, R., Stivaletta, N., Marinangeli, L., and Ori, G.G. (2006). Microbial signatures in sabkha
1042 evaporite deposits of Chott el Gharsa (Tunisia) and their astrobiological implications. *Planet.*
1043 *Space Sci.* 54, 726–736. doi: 10.1016/j.pss.2006.04.003
- 1044 Benison, K.C., and Karmanocky, F.J. III. (2014). Could microorganisms be preserved in Mars
1045 gypsum? Insights from terrestrial examples. *Geology* 42, 615–618. doi: 10.1130/G35542.1
- 1046 Bhartia, R., Beegle, L.W., DeFlores, L., Abbey, W., Razzell Hollis, J., and Uckert, K. (2021).
1047 Perseverance's Scanning Habitable Environments with Raman and Luminescence for Organics
1048 and Chemicals (SHERLOC) investigation. *Space Sci. Rev.* 217, 58. doi: 10.1007/s11214-021-
1049 00812-z
- 1050 Birgel, D., Guido, A., Liu, X., and Hinrichs, K.-U. (2014). Hypersaline conditions during deposition
1051 of the Calcare di Base revealed from archaeal di- and tetraether inventories. *Org. Geochem.* 77,
1052 11–21. doi: 10.1016/j.orggeochem.2014.09.002
- 1053 Boison, G., Mergel, A., Jolkver, H., and Bothe H. (2004). Bacterial life and dinitrogen fixation at a
1054 gypsum rock. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* 70, 7070–7077. doi: 10.1128/AEM.70.12.7070-
1055 7077.2004

- 1056 Bowden, S.A., and Parnell, J. (2007). Intracrystalline lipids within sulfates from the Houghton Impact
1057 Structure - Implications for survival of lipids on Mars. *Icarus* 187, 422–429. doi:
1058 10.1016/j.icarus.2006.10.013
- 1059 Briskin, M., and Schreiber, B.C. (1978). Authigenic gypsum in marine sediments. *Mar. Geol.* 28, 37–
1060 49. doi: 10.1016/0025-3227(78)90095-6
- 1061 Bultel-Poncé, V., Felix-Theodose, F., Sarthou, C. Ponge, J.-F. and Bodo B. (2004). New pigments
1062 from the terrestrial cyanobacterium *Scytonema* sp collected on the Mitaraka Inselberg, French
1063 Guyana. *J. Nat. Prod.* 67, 678–681. doi: 10.1021/np034031u.
- 1064 Cámara, B. (2012). Microbial colonization of gypsum and ignimbrite in the hyperarid region of the
1065 Atacama Desert. Doctoral thesis. Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, Madrid.
- 1066 Cámara, B., Souza-Egipsy, V., Ascaso, C., and Artieda O. (2016). Biosignatures and microbial
1067 fossils in endolithic microbial communities colonizing Ca-sulfate crusts in the Atacama Desert.
1068 *Chem. Geol.* 443, 22–31. doi: 10.1016/j.chemgeo.2016.09.019
- 1069 Canfield, D.E., Sørensen, K.B., and Oren, A. (2004). Biogeochemistry of a gypsum-encrusted
1070 microbial ecosystem. *Geobiology* 2, 133–150. doi: org/10.1111/j.1472-4677.2004.00029.x
- 1071 Carnevale, G., Gennari, R., Lozar, F. and Nataliocchio M. (2019). Living in a deep desiccated
1072 Mediterranean Sea: An overview of the Italian fossil record of the Messinian salinity crisis. *Boll.*
1073 *Soc. Paleontol. Ital.* 58, 109–140. doi: 10.4435/BSPI.2019.04
- 1074 Caselle, C., Baud, P., Kushnir, A.R.L., Reuschlé, T. and Bonetto, S.R.L. (2022). Influence of water
1075 on deformation and failure of gypsum rock. *J. Structur. Geol.* 163, 104722. doi:
1076 10.1016/j.jsg.2022.104722
- 1077 Casero, M.C., Meslier, V., Diruggiero J., and Wierzchos J. (2020). Atacama Desert endolithic
1078 microbiology. In: *Microbial Ecosystems in Central Andes Extreme Environments*. M.E. Farías,
1079 Rhinded. (Cham, Switzerland: Springer Nature), 51–72.
- 1080 Casero, M.-C., Meslier, V., DiRuggiero, J., Quesada, A., Ascaso, C., Artieda, O., (2021). The
1081 composition of endolithic communities in gypcrete is determined by the specific microhabitat
1082 architecture. *Biogeosciences* 18, 993–1007. doi: 10.5194/bg-18-993-2021
- 1083 Castaneda, I.S., and Schouten, S. (2011). A review of molecular organic proxies for examining
1084 modern and ancient lacustrine environments. *Quat. Sci. Rev.* 30, 2851–2891. doi:
1085 10.1016/j.quascirev.2011.07.009
- 1086 Caumette, P. (1993). Ecology and physiology of phototrophic bacteria and sulfate-reducing bacteria
1087 in salterns. *Experientia* 49, 473–481. doi: 10.1007/BF01955148
- 1088 Caumette, P., Matheron, R., Raymond, N., Relexans J.-C. (1994). Microbial mats in the hypersaline
1089 ponds of Mediterranean salterns (Salins-de-Giraud, France). *FEMS Microbiol. Ecol.* 13, 273–286.
1090 doi: 10.1111/j.1574-6941.1994.tb00074.x

- 1091 Cereceda, P., Larrain, H., Osses, P. and Salvador, M.S. (2008). The climate of the coast and fog zone
1092 in the Tarapacá Region, Atacama Desert, Chile. *Atmosph. Res.* 87, 301–311. doi:
1093 10.1016/j.atmosres.2007.11.011
- 1094 Cheng, Z.Y., Xiao, L., Wang, H.M., and Yang, H. (2017). Bacterial and archaeal lipids recovered
1095 from subsurface evaporites of Dalangtan Playa on the Tibetan Plateau and their astrobiological
1096 implications. *Astrobiology* 17, 1112–22. doi: 10.1089/ast.2016.1526
- 1097 Christeleit, E.C., Brandon, M.T., and Zhuang, G.S. (2015). Evidence for deep-water deposition of
1098 abyssal Mediterranean evaporites during the Messinian salinity crisis. *Earth Planet Sci Lett*
1099 427:226–223. doi: 10.1016/j.epsl.2015.06.060
- 1100 Christensen, P.R., Bandfield, J.L., Rogers, A.D., Glotch, R. T. D., Hamilton, V. E., Ruff, S. W. et al.
1101 (2008). Global mineralogy mapped from the Mars Global Surveyor Thermal Emission
1102 Spectrometer. In: *The Martian Surface, Composition, Mineralogy and Physical Properties*, Bell
1103 III, J.F. ed. (Cambridge, UK, Cambridge University Press) 195–220. doi:
1104 10.1017/CBO9780511536076.010
- 1105 Cipriani, M., Dominici, R., Costanzo, A., D'Antonio, M., and Guido A. (2021). A Messinian gypsum
1106 deposit in the Ionian Forearc Basin (Benestare, Calabria, Southern Italy): Origin and
1107 paleoenvironmental indications. *Minerals* 11, 1305. doi: 10.3390/min11121305
- 1108 Clark, B.C., and Baird, A.K. (1979). Is the Martian lithosphere sulfur rich? *J. Geophys. Res.* 84,
1109 8395–8402. doi: 10.1029/JB084iB14p08395
- 1110 Clark, B.C., Morris, R.V., McLennan, S.M., Gellert, R., Jolliff, B., and Knoll, A.H., et al. (2005).
1111 Chemistry and mineralogy of outcrops at Meridiani Planum. *Earth Planet. Sci. Lett.* 240, 73–94.
1112 doi: 10.1016/j.epsl.2005.09.040
- 1113 Cloutis, E., Applin, D., Connell, S., Kubanek, K. , Kuik, J., Parkinson, A., et al. (2021). A simulated
1114 rover exploration of a long-lived hypersaline spring environment: The East German Creek (MB,
1115 Canada) Mars analogue site. *Planet. Space Sci.* 195, 105130. doi: 10.1016/j.pss.2020.105130
- 1116 Cockell, C.S., McKay, C.P., Warren-Rhodes, Horneck, G. (2008). Ultraviolet radiation-induced
1117 limitation to epilithic microbial growth in arid deserts - Dosimetric experiments in the hyperarid
1118 core of the Atacama Desert. *J. Photochem. Photobiol. B: Biol.* 90, 79–87. doi:
1119 10.1016/j.pss.2020.105130
- 1120 Cockell, C.S., Osinski, G.R., Banerjee, N.R., Howard, K. T., Gilmour, I., and Watson J. S. et al.
1121 (2010). The microbe-mineral environment and gypsum neogenesis in a weathered polar
1122 evaporite. *Geobiology* 8, 293–308. doi: 10.1111/j.1472-4669.2010.00240.x
- 1123 Cody, A.M., and Cody, R.D. (1989a). Gypsum nucleation and crystal morphology in analog saline
1124 terrestrial environments. *J. Sediment. Petrol.* 59, 247–255.
- 1125 Cody, A.M., and Cody, R.D. (1989b). Evidence for micro-biological induction of {101} Montmartre
1126 twinning of gypsum (CaSO₄·2H₂O). *J. Cryst. Growth* 98, 721–30. doi: 10.1016/0022-
1127 0248(89)90310-2

- 1128 Cornee, A. (1982). Bactéries des saumures et des sediments des marais salants de Salin-de-Giraud
1129 (Sud de la France). *Géol. Médit.* 9, 369–389.
- 1130 Cornée, A. (1984). Etude préliminaire des bactéries des saumures et des sédiments des salins de
1131 Santa Pola (Espagne). Comparaison avec les marais salants de Salin-de-Giraud (Sud de la
1132 France). *Rev. Inv. Geol.* 38/39, 109–122.
- 1133 Cornée, A. (1989). Communautés benthiques à cyanobactéries des milieu hypersalés: intérêt
1134 géologique. *Bull. Soc. Bot. Fr. Actual. Bot.* 136, 131–145. doi:
1135 10.1080/01811789.1989.10826922
- 1136 Costanzo, A., Cipriani, M., Feely, M., Cianflogge G. (2019). Messinian twinned selenite from the
1137 Catanzaro Trough, Calabria, Southern Italy: field, petrographic and fluid inclusion perspectives.
1138 *Carbonates Evaporites* 34, 743–576. doi: 10.1007/s13146-019-00516-0
- 1139 Culka, A., Jehlička, J., Vandenabeele P., Edwards, H.G.M. (2011). The detection of biomarkers in
1140 evaporite matrices using a portable Raman instrument under Alpine conditions. *Spectrochim.*
1141 *Acta A, Mol. Biomol. Spectrosc.* 80, 8–13. doi: 10.1016/j.saa.2010.12.020
- 1142 Culka, A., Jehlička, J., and Strnad, L. (2012). Testing a portable Raman instrument: The detection of
1143 biomarkers in gypsum powdered matrix under gypsum crystals. *Spectrochim. Acta A, Mol.*
1144 *Biomol. Spectrosc.* 86, 347–350. doi: 10.1016/j.saa.2011.10.047
- 1145 Culka, A., Osterrothová, K., Hutchinson, I., Ingle, R., McHugh, M., and Oren, A. et al. (2014).
1146 Detection of pigments of halophilic endoliths from gypsum: Raman portable instrument and
1147 European Space Agency's prototype analysis. *Phil. Trans. R. Soc. A* 372, 20140203. doi:
1148 10.1098/rsta.2014.0203
- 1149 Culka, A., Jehlička, J., Ascaso, C., and Artieda O. (2017). Raman microspectrometric study of
1150 pigments in melanized fungi from the hyperarid Atacama desert gypsum crust. *J. Raman*
1151 *Spectrosc.* 48, 1487–1493. doi: 10.1002/jrs.5137
- 1152 Culka, A., Jehlicka, J., Oren, A., Rousaki, A., and Vandenabeele, P. (2022). Fast outdoor screening
1153 and discrimination of carotenoids of halophilic microorganisms using miniaturized Raman
1154 spectrometers. *Spectrochim. Acta A, Mol. Biomol. Spectrosc.* 276, 121156. doi:
1155 10.1016/j.saa.2022.121156
- 1156 De la Puente, L., Ferrio, J.P., and Palacio, S. (2022). Disentangling water sources in a gypsum plant
1157 community. Gypsum crystallization water is a key source of water for shallow-rooted plants. *Ann.*
1158 *Bot.* 129, 87–100. doi: 10.1093/aob/mcab107
- 1159 Dela Pierre, F., Natalicchio, M., Ferrando, S., and Giustetto R. (2015). Are the large filamentous
1160 microfossils preserved in Messinian gypsum colorless sulfide-oxidizing bacteria? *Geology* 43,
1161 855–858. doi: 10.1130/G37018.1
- 1162 Demaret, L., Hutchinson, I.B., Eppe, G., Malherbe, C. (2020). Analytical strategy for representative
1163 subsampling of Raman-based robotic planetary exploration missions: The case study of solid
1164 dispersions of β -carotene and L-cysteine in gypsum. *J. Raman Spectrosc.* 51, 1624–1635. doi:
1165 10.1002/jrs.5705

- 1166 Diloreto, Z., Ahmad, M.S., Al-Kuwari, H.A.S., Sadooni, F., Bontognali, T.R.R., and Dittrich, M.
1167 (2023). Raman spectroscopic and microbial study of biofilms hosted gypsum deposits in the
1168 hypersaline wetlands: Astrobiological perspective. *Astrobiology* 23, 991-1005. doi:
1169 10.1089/ast.2023.0003
- 1170 DiRuggiero, J., Wierzchos, J., Robinson, C.K., Souterre, T., Ravel, J., and Artieda, O. (2013).
1171 Microbial colonization of chasmoendolithic habitats in the hyper-arid zone of the Atacama
1172 Desert. *Biogeosciences* 10, 2439–2450. doi: 10.5194/bg-10-2439-2013
- 1173 Dong, H.L., Rech, J.A., Jiang, H.C. , and Sun, H.J. (2007). Endolithic cyanobacteria in soil gypsum:
1174 Occurrences in Atacama (Chile), Mojave (United States), and Al-Jafr Basin (Jordan) deserts. *J.*
1175 *Geophys. Res. – Biogeosci.* 112, G02030. doi: 10.1029/2006JG000385
- 1176 Douchi D, Larbi GS, Fel B et al. Dryland endolithic Chroococcidiopsis and temperate fresh water
1177 Synechocystis have distinct membrane lipid and photosynthesis acclimation strategies upon
1178 desiccation and temperature increase. *Plant Cell Physiol*; <https://doi.org/10.1093/pcp/pcad139>
- 1179 Douglas, S. (2004). Microbial biosignatures in evaporite deposits: Evidence from Death Valley,
1180 California. *Planet. Space Sci.* 52, 223–227. doi: 10.1016/j.pss.2003.08.005
- 1181 Douglas, S. (2005). Mineralogical footprints of microbial life. *Am. J. Sci.* 305, 503–525. doi:
1182 10.2475/ajs.305.6-8.503
- 1183 Edwards, H.G.M., Jorge Villar, S.E., Parnell, J., Cockell, C.S., and Lee P. (2005a). Raman
1184 spectroscopic analysis of cyanobacterial gypsum halotrophs and relevance for sulfate deposits on
1185 Mars. *Analyst* 130, 917–923. doi: 10.1039/b503533c
- 1186 Edwards, H.G.M., Moody, C.D., Jorge Villar, S.E., and Wynn-Williams, D.D. (2005b). Raman
1187 spectroscopic detection of key biomarkers of cyanobacteria and lichen symbiosis in extreme
1188 Antarctic habitats: Evaluation for Mars Lander missions. *Icarus* 174, 560–571. doi:
1189 10.1016/j.icarus.2004.07.029
- 1190 Edwards, H.G.M., Mohsin, M.A., Sadooni, F.N., Nik Hassan, N.F., and Munshi, T. (2006). Life in
1191 the sabkha: Raman spectroscopy of halotrophic extremophiles of relevance to planetary
1192 exploration. *Analyt. Bioanalyt. Chem.* 385, 46–56. doi: 10.1007/s00216-006-0396-3
- 1193 Edwards, H.G.M., Jorge Villar, S.E., Pullan, D., and Hargreaves, M. (2007). Morphological
1194 biosignatures from relict fossilised sedimentary geological specimens: a Raman spectroscopic
1195 study. *J. Raman Spectrosc.* 38, 1352–1361. doi: 10.1002/jrs.1775
- 1196 Edwards, H.G.M., Němečková, K., Jehlička, J. and Culka, A. (2023). Scytonin in gypsum endolithic
1197 colonisation: First Raman spectroscopic detection of a new spectral biosignature for terrestrial
1198 astrobiological analogues and for exobiological mission database extension. *Spectrochim. Acta A,*
1199 *Mol. Biomol. Spectrosc.* 292, 122406. doi: 10.1016/j.saa.2023.122406
- 1200 Ertekin, E., Meslier, V., Browning, A. and Treadgold, J. (2021). Rock structure drives the taxonomic
1201 and functional diversity of endolithic microbial communities in extreme environments. *Environ.*
1202 *Microbiol.* 23, 3937–3956. doi: 10.1111/1462-2920.15287

- 1203 Fairén, A.G., Davila, A.F., Lim, D., and Bramall N. (2010). Astrobiology through the ages of Mars:
1204 the study of terrestrial analogues to understand the habitability of Mars. *Astrobiology* 10, 821–
1205 843. doi: 10.1089/ast.2009.0440
- 1206 Farías, M.E., Contreras, M., Rasuk, M.C., Kurth, D., Flores, M.R., Poiré, D.G. et al. (2014).
1207 Characterization of bacterial diversity associated to microbial mats, gypsum evaporites, and
1208 carbonate microbialites in thalassic wetlands: Tebenquiche and La Brava at Salar de Atacama,
1209 Chile. *Extremophiles* 18, 311–329. doi: 10.1007/s00792-013-0617-6
- 1210 Farías, M.E., Villafañe, P.G., Lencina, A.I. (2020). Integral prospection of Andean microbial
1211 ecosystem project. In: *Microbial Ecosystems in Central Andes Extreme Environments*. ed. M.E.
1212 Farías (Cham, Switzerland: Springer International Publishing), 245–259. doi: 10.1007/978-3-030-
1213 36192-1_17
- 1214 Farley, K.A., Williford, K.H., Stack, K.M., Bhartia, R., Chen, A., de la Torre, M. et al. (2020). Mars
1215 2020 mission overview. *Space Sci. Rev.* 216, 142. doi: 10.1007/s11214-020-00762-y
- 1216 Fishbaugh, K.E. and Hvidberg, C.S. (2006). Martian north polar layered deposits stratigraphy:
1217 Implications for accumulation rates and flow. *J. Geophys. Res. Planets* 111, E06012. doi:
1218 10.1029/2005JE002571
- 1219 Garcia-Ruiz, J.M., Villasuso, R., Ayora, C., and Canals, A. (2007). Formation of natural gypsum
1220 megacrystals in Naica, Mexico. *Geology* 35, 327–330. doi: 10.1130/G23393A.1
- 1221 Glass, B., Bergman, D., Parro, V., Kobayashi, L., Stoker, C., Quinn, R., et al. (2023). The Atacama
1222 Rover Astrobiology Drilling Studies (ARADS) Project. *Astrobiology* 23, 1245-1258.
1223 doi:10.1089/ast.2022.0126
- 1224 Golubic, S., Friedmann, I., Schneider, J. (1981). The lithobionthic ecological niche, with special
1225 reference to microorganisms. *J.Sediment. Petrol.* 51, 475-478.
- 1226 Gorbushina, A. Life on the rocks. (2007). *Environ. Microbiol.* 9, 1613–1631. doi: 10.1111/j.1462-
1227 2920.2007.01301.x
- 1228 Grotzinger, J.P., Arvidson, R.E., Bell, III J.F. and Calvin W.M. (2005). Stratigraphy and
1229 sedimentology of a dry to wet eolian depositional system, Burns formation, Meridiani Planum,
1230 Mars. *Earth Planet. Sci. Lett.* 240, 11–72. doi: 10.1016/j.epsl.2005.09.039
- 1231 Haffert, L., and Haeckel, M. (2019). Quantification of non-ideal effects on diagenetic processes along
1232 extreme salinity gradients at the Mercator mud volcano in the Gulf of Cadiz. *Geochim.*
1233 *Cosmochim. Acta* 244, 366–382. doi: 10.1016/j.gca.2018.09.038
- 1234 Harris, C.M., Maclay, M.T., Lutz, K.A., Vinitra N., Ortega Dominguez, N.A., Leavitt, W.D. (2022).
1235 Remote and *in-situ* characterization of Mars analogs: Coupling scales to improve the search for
1236 microbial signatures on Mars. *Front. Astron. Space Sci.* 9, 849078. doi:
1237 10.3389/fspas.2022.849078
- 1238 Hauer, T., Muhlsteinová, R., Bohunická, M., Kaštovský, J., Mareš, J. (2015). Diversity of cyanobacteria on
1239 rock surfaces. *Biodivers. Conservat.* 24, 759-779. doi.: 10.1007/s10531-015-0890-z

- 1240 Huang, W., Ertekin, E., Wang, T. and Kisailus D. (2020). Mechanism of water extraction from
1241 gypsum rock by desert colonizing microorganisms. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* 117, 10681–
1242 10687. doi: 10.1073/pnas.2001613117
- 1243 Huang, W., Wang, T., Perez-Fernandez, C., DiRuggiero, J., Kisailus, D. (2022). Iron acquisition and
1244 mineral transformation by cyanobacteria living in extreme environments. *Materials Today Bio.*
1245 17, 100493. doi: 10.1016/j.mtbio.2022.100493
- 1246 Hughes, K.A., and Lawley, B. (2003). A novel Antarctic microbial endolithic community within
1247 gypsum crusts. *Environ. Microbiol.* 5, 555–565. doi: 10.1046/j.1462-2920.2003.00439.x
- 1248 Huguen, C., Foucher, J.P., and Mascle, J. (2009). Menes caldera, a highly active site of brine seepage
1249 in the Eastern Mediterranean sea: "In situ" observations from the NAUTINIL expedition (2003).
1250 *Mar. Geol.* 261, 138–152. doi: 10.1016/j.margeo.2009.02.005
- 1251 Ionescu, D., Lipski, A., Altendorf, K. And Oren A. (2007). Characterization of the endoevaporitic
1252 microbial communities in a hypersaline gypsum crust by fatty acid analysis. *Hydrobiologia* 576,
1253 15–26. doi: 10.1007/s10750-006-0289-7
- 1254 Isaji, Y., Yoshimura, T., Kuroda, J., Tamenori, Y., Jiménez-Espejo, F.J., Lugli, S. (2019). Biomarker
1255 records and mineral compositions of the Messinian halite and K-Mg salts from Sicily. *Progr.*
1256 *Earth Planet. Sci* 6, 60. doi: 10.1186/s40645-019-0306-x
- 1257 Jafarzadeh, A.A., and Burnham, C.P. (1992). Gypsum crystals in soils. *Eur. J. Soil Sci.* 43, 409–420.
1258 doi: 10.1111/j.1365-2389.1992.tb00147.x
- 1259 Jahnke, L.L., and Des Marais, D.J. (2019). Carbon isotopic composition of lipid biomarkers from an
1260 endoevaporitic gypsum crust microbial mat reveals cycling of mineralized organic carbon.
1261 *Geobiology* 17, 643–659. doi: 10.1111/gbi.12355
- 1262 Jahnke, L.L., Turk-Kubo, K.A., Parenteau, M.N., Green, S. J., Kubo, M. D.Y., Vogel, M. et al.
1263 (2014). Molecular and lipid biomarker analysis of a gypsum-hosted endoevaporitic microbial
1264 community. *Geobiology* 12, 62–82. doi: 10.1111/gbi.12068
- 1265 Jehlička, J., and Culka, A. (2022). Critical evaluation of portable Raman spectrometers: From rock
1266 outcrops and planetary analogs to cultural heritage-A review. *Analyt. Chim. Acta* 1209, 339027.
1267 doi: 10.1016/j.aca.2021.339027
- 1268 Jehlička, J., and Oren, A. (2013). Use of a handheld Raman spectrometer for fast screening of
1269 microbial pigments in cultures of halophilic microorganisms and in microbial communities in
1270 hypersaline environments in nature. *J. Raman Spectrosc.* 44, 1285–1291. doi: 10.1002/jrs.4362
- 1271 Jehlička, J., Edwards, H.G.M., and Oren, A. (2014). Raman spectroscopy of microbial pigments.
1272 *Appl. Env. Microbiol.* 80, 3286–3295. doi: 10.1128/AEM.00699-14
- 1273 Jehlička, J., Culka, A., Mana, L., and Oren, A. (2018). Using a portable Raman spectrometer to
1274 detect carotenoids of halophilic prokaryotes in synthetic inclusions in NaCl, KCl, and sulfates.
1275 *Analyt. Bioanalyt. Chem.* 410, 4437–4443. doi: 10.1007/s00216-018-1098-3

- 1276 Jehlička, J., Culka, A., and Mareš, J. (2020). Raman spectroscopic screening of cyanobacterial
1277 chasmoliths from crystalline gypsum—The Messinian crisis sediments from Southern Sicily. *J.*
1278 *Raman Spectrosc.* 51, 1802–1812. doi: 10.1002/jrs.5671
- 1279 Jehlička, J., Culka, A., Němečková, K., and Mareš J. (2023). Using Raman spectroscopy to detect
1280 scytonemin of epiliths and endoliths from marble, serpentinite and gypsum. *J. Raman Spectrosc.*
1281 54, 1280-1296. doi: 10.1002/jrs.6514.
- 1282 Jorge Villar, S.E., Edwards, H.G.M., and Cockell, C.S. Raman spectroscopy of endoliths from
1283 Antarctic cold desert environments. *Analyst* (2005a). 130, 156–162. doi: 10.1039/B410854J
- 1284 Jorge Villar, S.E., Edwards, H.G.M., and Worland, M.R. (2005b). Comparative evaluation of Raman
1285 spectroscopy at different wavelengths for extremophile exemplars. *Orig Life Evol Biosph* 35,
1286 489–506. doi: 10.1007/s11084-005-3528-4
- 1287 Kah, L.C., Stack, K.M., Eigenbrode, J.L. Yingst, A., Edgett, K.S. (2018). Syndepositional
1288 precipitation of calcium sulfate in Gale Crater, Mars. *Terra Nova* 30, 431–439. doi:
1289 10.1111/ter.12359
- 1290 Kasprzyk, A., Jasińska, B. (1998). Isotopic composition of the crystallization water of gypsum in the
1291 Badenian of the northern Carpathian Foredeep: a case study from the cores Przyborów 1 and
1292 Strzegom 143. *Geol. Quart.* 42, 10.
- 1293 Kedar, L., Kashman, Y., and Oren, A. (2002). Mycosporine-2-glycine is the major mycosporine-like
1294 amino acid in a unicellular cyanobacterium (*Euhalothece* sp.) isolated from a gypsum crust in a
1295 hypersaline saltern pond. *FEMS Microbiol. Lett.* 208, 233–237. doi: 10.1111/j.1574-
1296 6968.2002.tb11087.x
- 1297 Keely, B.J., Blake, S.R., Schaeffer, P., and Maxwell, J. R. (1995). Distributions of pigments in the
1298 organic matter of marls from the Vena del Gesso evaporitic sequence. *Org. Geochem.* 23, 527–
1299 539. doi: 10.1016/0146-6380(95)00046-H
- 1300 Kenig, F., Hudson, J.D., Sinninghe Damsté, J.S., Popp, B.N. (2004). Intermittent
1301 euxinia:Reconciliation of a Jurassic black shale with its biofacies. *Geology* 32, 421-424. doi:
1302 101130/G20356.1
- 1303 Lara, Y.J., McCann, A., Malherbe, C. François, C., Demoulin, C.F., Sforza, M.C., et al. (2022).
1304 Characterization of the halochromic gloeocapsin pigment, a cyanobacterial biosignature for
1305 paleobiology and astrobiology. *Astrobiology* 22, 735–754. doi: 10.1089/ast.2021.0061
- 1306 López-Lozano, N.E., Eguiarte, L.E., Bonilla-Rosso, G., García-Oliva, F., Martínez-Piedragil, C.,
1307 Rooks, C. et al. (2012). Bacterial communities and the nitrogen cycle in the gypsum soils of
1308 Cuatro Ciéngas Basin, Coahuila: a Mars analogue. *Astrobiology* 12, 699–709. doi:
1309 10.1089/ast.2012.0840
- 1310 Lugli, S., Manzi, V., Roveri, M. B., and Schreiber C. (2010). The Primary Lower Gypsum in the
1311 Mediterranean: A new facies interpretation for the first stage of the Messinian salinity crisis.
1312 *Paleogeogr. Palaeoclimat. Palaeoecol.* 297, 83–99. doi: 10.1016/j.palaeo.2010.07.017

- 1313 Macedo, M.F., Miller, A.Z., Dionísio A., Sais-Jimenez, C. (2009). Biodiversity of cyanobacteria and
1314 green algae on monuments in the Mediterranean Basin: an overview. *Microbiology-SGM* 155,
1315 3475-3490. doi: 10.1099/mic.0.032508-0
- 1316 Malherbe, C., Hutchinson, I.B., McHugh, M., Ingley, R., Jehlička, J., and Edwards H.G. M. (2017).
1317 Accurate differentiation of carotenoid pigments using flight representative Raman spectrometers.
1318 *Astrobiology* 17, 351–362. doi: 10.1089/ast.2016.1547
- 1319 Marshall, C.P., Carter, E.A., Leuko, S., and Javaux, E.J. (2006). Vibrational spectroscopy of extant
1320 and fossil microbes: Relevance for the astrobiological exploration of Mars. *Vib. Spectrosc.* 41,
1321 182–189. doi: 10.1016/j.vibspec.2006.01.008
- 1322 Martinez-Frias, J., Amaral, G., and Vázquez, L. (2006). Astrobiological significance of minerals on
1323 Mars surface environment. *Rev. Environ. Sci. Biotechnol.* 5, 219–231. doi: 10.1007/978-1-4020-
1324 6285-8_4
- 1325 McGonigle, J.M., Bernau, J.A., Bowen, B.B. and Brazelton E.J. (2019). Robust archaeal and
1326 bacterial communities inhabit shallow subsurface sediments of the Bonneville Salt Flats. *mSphere*
1327 4, e00378-19. doi: 10.1128/mSphere.00378-19
- 1328 McKay, C.P., Friedmann, E.I., Gomez-Silva, B., Cáceres-Villanueva, L., Andersen, D.T. and
1329 Landheim R. (2003). Temperature and moisture conditions for life in the of observations
1330 including the El Nino of 1997–1998. *Astrobiology*, 393–406. doi: 10.1089/153110703769016460
- 1331 McLennan, S.M. Bell III, J.F., Calvin, W.M., Christensen, P.R., Clark, B.C., de Souza, P.A., et al.
1332 (2005) Provenance and diagenesis of the evaporite-bearing Burns formation, Meridiani Planum,
1333 Mars. *Earth Planet. Sci. Lett.* 24095 – 121. doi:10.1016/j.epsl.2005.09.041
- 1334 Meslier, V., Casero, M.C., Dailey, M. Wierzchos, J., Ascaso, C., Artieda, O. et al. (2018).
1335 Fundamental drivers for endolithic microbial community assemblies in the hyperarid Atacama
1336 Desert. *Environ. Microbiol.* 20, 1765–1781. doi: 10.1111/1462-2920.14106
- 1337 Moreno-Paz, M., dos Santos Severino, R.S., Sánchez-García, L., Manchado, J.M., García-
1338 Villadangos, M., Aguirre, J., et al. (2023). Life detection and microbial biomarker profiling with
1339 signs of life detector-life detector chip during a mars drilling simulation campaign in the
1340 hyperarid core of the Atacama Desert. *Astrobiology* 23, 1259-1283. doi: 0.1089/ast.2021.0174
- 1341 Nachon, M., Clegg, S.M., Mangold, N., Schröder, S ; Kah, L.C., Dromart, G. et al. 2014 Calcium
1342 sulfate veins characterized by ChemCam/Curiosity at Gale crater, Mars. *J. Geophys. Res., Planets*
1343 119,1991-2016. doi:10.1002/2013JE004588
- 1344 Natalicchio, M., Birgel, D., Peckmann, J. Lozar, F., Carnevale, G., Liu, X., et al. (2017). An archaeal
1345 biomarker record of paleoenvironmental change across the onset of the Messinian salinity crisis
1346 in the absence of evaporites (Piedmont Basin, Italy). *Org. Geochem.* 13, 242–253. doi:
1347 10.1016/j.orggeochem.2017.08.014
- 1348 Natalicchio, M., Pellegrino, L., Clari, P. and Pastero L. (2021). Gypsum lithofacies and stratigraphic
1349 architecture of a Messinian marginal basin (Piedmont Basin, NW Italy). *Sediment. Geol.* 425,
1350 106009. doi: 10.1016/j.sedgeo.2021.106009

- 1351 Natalicchio, M., Birgel, D., Dela Pierre, F., Ziegenbalg, S., Hoffmann-Sell, L., Gier, S. et al. (2022).
 1352 Messinian bottom-grown selenitic gypsum: An archive of microbial life. *Geobiology* 20, 3–21.
 1353 doi: 10.1111/gbi.12464
- 1354 Němečková, K., Jehlička, J. and Culka, A. (2020). Fast screening of carotenoids of gypsum endoliths
 1355 using portable Raman spectrometer (Messinian gypsum, Sicily). *J. Raman Spectrosc.* 51, 1127–
 1356 1137. doi: 10.1002/jrs.5891
- 1357 Němečková, K., Culka, A., Němec, I. Edwards, H.G.M., Mareš, J., and Jehlička, J. (2021). Raman
 1358 spectroscopic search for scytonemin and gloeocapsin in endolithic colonizations in large gypsum
 1359 crystals. *J. Raman Spectrosc.* 52, 2633–2647. doi: 10.1002/jrs.6186
- 1360 Němečková, K., Culka, A., and Jehlička, J. (2022). Detecting pigments from gypsum endoliths using
 1361 Raman spectroscopy: From field prospection to laboratory studies. *J. Raman Spectrosc.* 53, 630–
 1362 644. doi: 10.1002/jrs.6144
- 1363 Němečková, K., Mareš, J., Prochazková, L., Culka, A., Košek, F., Wierzchos, J., et al. (2023).
 1364 Gypsum endolithic phototrophs under moderate climate (Southern Sicily): their diversity and
 1365 pigment composition. *Front. Microbiol.* 14, 1175066. 10.3389/fmicb.2023.1175066
- 1366 Nimis, P. L., Poelt J., and Tretiach M. (1996). Lichens from the Gypsum Park of the Northern
 1367 Apennines (Italy). *Cryptogam. Mycol.* 17, 67–82.
- 1368 Oren, A. (1997). Mycosporine-like amino acids as osmotic solutes in a community of halophilic
 1369 cyanobacteria. *Geomicrobiol. J.* 14, 233–242. doi: 10.1080/01490459709378046
- 1370 Oren, A. (2009). Saltern evaporation ponds as model systems for the study of primary production
 1371 processes under hypersaline conditions. *Aquat. Microb. Ecol.* 56, 193–204. doi:
 1372 10.3354/ame01297
- 1373 Oren, A., Köhl, M. and Karsten, U. (1995). An endoevaporitic microbial mat within a gypsum crust:
 1374 zonation of phototrophs, photopigments, and light penetration. *Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.* 128, 151–
 1375 159. doi: 10.3354/meps128151
- 1376 Oren, A., Ionescu, D., Lipski, A., and Altendorf, K. (2005). Fatty acid analysis of a layered
 1377 community of cyanobacteria developing in a hypersaline gypsum crust. *Algol. Stud.* 117, 339–
 1378 347. doi: 10.1127/1864-1318/2005/0117-0339
- 1379 Oren, A., Sørensen, K.B., Canfield, D.E., Teske, A.P., Ionescu, D., Lipski, A., et al. (2009).
 1380 Microbial communities and processes within a hypersaline gypsum crust in a saltern evaporation
 1381 pond (Eilat, Israel). *Hydrobiologia* 626, 15–26. doi: 10.1007/s10750-009-9734-8
- 1382 Oren, A., Elevi Bardavid, R., Kandel, N., Aizenshtat, Z., and Jehlicka, J. (2013). Glycine betaine is
 1383 the main organic osmotic solute in a stratified microbial community in a hypersaline evaporitic
 1384 gypsum crust. *Extremophiles* 17, 445–451. doi: 10.1007/s00792-013-0522-z
- 1385 Ortí Cabo, F., Puejo Mur, J.J., and Truc, G. (1984). Las salinas marítimas de Santa Pola (Alicante,
 1386 España). Breve introducción al estudio de un medio natural controlado de sedimentación
 1387 evaporítica somera. *Rev. Inv. Geol.* 38/39, 9–29.

- 1388 Ossorio, M., Van Driessche, A.E.S., Pérez, P., and García-Ruiz, J.M. (2014). The gypsum-anhydrite
1389 paradox revisited. *Chem. Geol.* 386, 16–21. doi: 10.1016/j.chemgeo.2014.07.026
- 1390 Osterloo, M.M., Hamilton, V.E., and Bandfield, J.L. (2008). Chloride-bearing materials in the
1391 southern highlands of Mars. *Science* 319, 1651–1654. doi: 10.1126/science.1150690
- 1392 Osterrothová, K., and Jehlička, J. (2011). Feasibility of Raman microspectroscopic identification of
1393 biomarkers through gypsum crystals. *Spectrochim. Acta A Mol. Biomol. Spectrosc.* 80, 96–101.
1394 doi: 10.1016/j.saa.2010.12.085
- 1395 Palacio, S., Azorín, J., Montserrat-Martí, G., Ferrio, J.P. (2014). The crystallization water of gypsum
1396 rocks is a relevant water source for plants. *Nat. Commun.* 5, 4660. doi: 10.1038/ncomms5660
- 1397 Panieri, G., Lugli, S., Manzi, V., Palinska, K.A., and Roveri, M. (2008). Microbial communities in
1398 Messinian evaporite deposits of the Vena del Gesso (northern Apennines, Italy). *Stratigraphy* 5,
1399 343–352. doi: 10.29041/strat.05.3.09
- 1400 Panieri, G., Lugli, S., Manzi, V., Roveri, M., Schreiber, B.C., and Palinska, K.A. (2010). Ribosomal
1401 RNA gene fragments from fossilized cyanobacteria identified in primary gypsum from the late
1402 Miocene, Italy. *Geobiology* 8, 101–111. doi: 10.1111/j.1472-4669.2009.00230.x
- 1403 Parnell, J., Lee, P., Cockell, C.S., and Osinski, G.R. (2004). Microbial colonization in impact-
1404 generated hydrothermal sulphate deposits, Haughton impact structure, and implications for
1405 sulphates on Mars. *Int. J. Astrobiol.* 3, 247–256. doi: 10.1017/S1473550404001995
- 1406 Pellegrino, L., Natalicchio, M., Abe, K., Jordan, R.W., Favero-Longo, S.E., Ferrando, S., et al.
1407 (2021). Tiny, glassy, and rapidly trapped: The nano-sized planktic diatoms in Messinian (late
1408 Miocene) gypsum. *Geology* 49, 1369–1374. doi: 10.1130/G49342.1
- 1409 Pirlet, H., Wehrmann, L.M., Brunner, B., Frank, N., Dewanckele, J., Van Rooij, D., et al. (2010).
1410 Diagenetic formation of gypsum and dolomite in a cold-water coral mound in the Porcupine
1411 Seabight, off Ireland. *Sedimentology* 57, 786–805. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-3091.2009.01119.x
- 1412 Poca, M., Coomans, O., Urcelay, C., Zeballos, S.R., Bodé, S., and Boeckx, P. (2019). Isotope
1413 fractionation during root water uptake by *Acacia caven* is enhanced by arbuscular mycorrhizas.
1414 *Plant Soil* 441, 485–497. doi: 10.1007/s11104-019-04139-1
- 1415 Prášil, O., Bína, D., Medová, H., Řeháková, K., Zapomělová, E., Veselá, J. et al. (2009). Emission
1416 spectroscopy and kinetic fluorimetry studies of the phototrophic microbial communities along the
1417 salinity gradient in the solar saltern evaporation ponds of Eilat, Israel. *Aquat. Microb. Ecol.* 56,
1418 285–296. doi: [10.3354/ame01311](https://doi.org/10.3354/ame01311)
- 1419 Preston, L.J., Barcenilla, R., Dartnell, L.R., Kucukkilic-Stephens, E., and Olsson-Francis, K. (2020).
1420 Infrared spectroscopic detection of biosignatures at Lake Tirez, Spain: Implications for Mars.
1421 *Astrobiology* 20, 15–25. doi: 10.1089/ast.2019.2106
- 1422 Proteau, P.J., Gerwick, W.H., Garcia-Pichel, F., and Castenholz, R. (1993). The structure of
1423 scytonemin, an ultraviolet sunscreen pigment from the sheaths of cyanobacteria. *Experientia* 49,
1424 825–829. doi: 10.1007/BF01923559

- 1425 Rapin, W., Ehlmann, B.L., Dromart, G., Schieber, J., Thomas, N.H., Fischer, W.W., et al. (2019). An
1426 interval of high salinity in ancient Gale crater lake on Mars. *Nat. Geosci.* 12, 889–895. doi:
1427 10.1038/s41561-019-0458-8
- 1428 Rasuk, M.C., Kurth, D., Flores, M.R., Contreras, M., Novoa, F., Poire, D., et al. (2014). Microbial
1429 characterization of microbial ecosystems associated to evaporites domes of gypsum in Salar de
1430 Llamara in Atacama Desert. *Microb. Ecol.* 68, 483–494. doi: 10.1007/s00248-014-0431-4
- 1431 Rasuk, M.C., Leiva, M.C., Kurth, D., and Farías, M.E. (2020). “Complete characterization of
1432 stratified ecosystems of the Salar de Llamara (Atacama Desert),” in *Microbial Ecosystems in
1433 Central Andes Extreme Environments*, ed. Farías M.E. (Cham, Switzerland: Springer
1434 International Publishing), 153–164.
- 1435 Rhind, T., Ronholm, J., Berg, B., Mann, P., Applin, D., Stromberg, J., et al. (2014). Gypsum-hosted
1436 endolithic communities of the Lake St. Martin Impact Crater, Manitoba, Canada:
1437 Characterization, detectability, and implications for Mars. *Int. J. Astrobiol.* 13, 366–377. doi:
1438 10.1017/S1473550414000378
- 1439 Rouchy, J.M., and Monty, C.L.V. (1981). “Stromatolites and cryptoalgal laminites associated with
1440 Messinian gypsum in Cyprus,” in *Phanerozoic Stromatolites*, ed. Monty, C.L.V., (Berlin:
1441 Springer), 155–180.
- 1442 Rouchy, J.M., and Monty, C. (2000). “Gypsum microbial sediments: Neogene and modern
1443 examples,” in *Microbial Sediments*, eds. Riding, R.E., Awramik, S.M., (Berlin, Heidelberg:
1444 Springer), 209–216.
- 1445 Rull, F., Maurice, F., Hutchinson, I., Moral, A., Perez, C., Diaz, C., et al. (2017). The Raman laser
1446 spectrometer for the ExoMars Rover Mission to Mars. *Astrobiology* 17, 627–654. doi:
1447 10.1089/ast.2016.1567
- 1448 Russell, N.C., Edwards, H.G.M., and Wynn-Williams, D.D. (1998). FT-Raman spectroscopic
1449 analysis of endolithic microbial communities from Beacon sandstone in Victoria Land,
1450 Antarctica. *Antarctic. Sci.* 10, 63–74. doi: 10.1017/S0954102098000091
- 1451 Řeháková, K., Zapomělová, E., Prášil, O., Veselá, J., Medová, H., and Oren, A. (2009). Composition
1452 changes of phototrophic microbial communities along the salinity gradient in the solar saltern
1453 evaporation ponds of Eilat, Israel. *Hydrobiologia* 636, 77–88. doi:[10.1007/s10750-009-9936-0](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10750-009-9936-0)
- 1454 Sabino, M., Schefuss, E., Natalicchio, M., Dela Pierre, F., Birgel, D., Bortels, D., et al. (2020).
1455 Climatic and hydrologic variability in the northern Mediterranean across the onset of the
1456 Messinian salinity crisis. *Paleogeogr. Paleoclimatol. Paleoecol.* 545, 109632. doi:
1457 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109632
- 1458 Sabino, M., Dela Pierre, F., Natalicchio, M., Birgel, D., Gier, S., and Peckmann, J. (2021). The
1459 response of water column and sedimentary environments to the advent of the Messinian salinity
1460 crisis: insights from an onshore deep-water section (Govone, NW Italy). *Geol. Mag.* 158, 825–
1461 841. doi: 10.1017/S0016756820000874

- 1462 Scheller, E.L., Hollis, J.R., Cardarelli, E.L., Steele, A., Beegle, L.W., Bhartia, R., *et al.* (2022).
1463 Aqueous alteration processes in Jezero crater, Mars-implications for organic geochemistry.
1464 *Science* 378, 1105–1110. doi: 10.1126/science.abo5204
- 1465 Schopf, J.W., Farmer, J.D., Foster, I.S., Kudryavtsev, A.B., Gallardo, V.A., and Espinoza, C. (2012).
1466 Gypsum-permineralized microfossils and their relevance to the search for life on Mars.
1467 *Astrobiology* 12, 619–633. doi: 10.1089/ast.2012.0827
- 1468 Schreiber, B.C., Friedman, G.M., Decima, A., and Schreiber, E. (1976). Depositional environments
1469 of Upper Miocene (Messinian) evaporite deposits of three Sicilian basins. *Sedimentology* 23,
1470 729–760. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-3091.1976.tb00107.x
- 1471 Schulze-Makuch, D., Lipus, D., Arens, F.L., Baque, M., Bornemann, T.L.V., de Vera, J.P. *et al.*
1472 (2021). Microbial hotspots in lithic microhabitats inferred from DNA fractionation and
1473 metagenomics in the Atacama Desert. *Microorganisms* 9, 1038. doi:
1474 10.3390/microorganisms9051038
- 1475 Shen, J.X., Chen, Y., Sun, Y., Liu, L., Pan, Y.X., and Lin, W. (2022). Detection of biosignatures in
1476 terrestrial analogs of Martian regions: Strategic and technical assessments. *Earth Planet Phys.*
1477 6, 431–450. doi: 10.26464/epp2022042
- 1478 Sinha, R., and Raymahashay, B.C. (2004). Evaporite mineralogy and geochemical evolution of the
1479 Sambhar Salt Lake, Rajasthan, India. *Sediment Geol.* 166, 59–71. doi:
1480 10.1016/j.sedgeo.2003.11.021
- 1481 Sinninghe Damsté, J. S., Kenig, F., Koopmans, M. E., Köster, J., Schouten, S., Hayes, J. M. *et al.*
1482 (1995). Evidence for gammacerane as an indicator of water column stratification.
1483 *Geochim. Cosmochim. Acta*, 59, 1895-1990. doi: 10.1016/0016-7037(95)00073
- 1484 Sinninghe Damsté, J.S., Schouten, S., Hopmans, E.C., van Duin, A.C.T., and Geenevasen, J.A.J.
1485 (2002). Crenarchaeol: the characteristic core glycerol dibiphytanyl glycerol tetraether membrane lipid
1486 of cosmopolitan pelagic crenarchaeota. *J. Lipid Res.* 43, 1641–1651. doi: 10.1194/jlr.M200148-
1487 JLR200
- 1488 Sørensen, K.B., Canfield, D.E., and Oren, A. (2004). Salinity responses of benthic microbial
1489 communities in a solar saltern (Eilat, Israel). *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* 70, 1608–1616. doi:
1490 10.1128/AEM.70.3.1608-1616.2004
- 1491 Sørensen, K.B., Canfield, D.E., Teske, A.P., and Oren, A. (2005). Community composition of a
1492 hypersaline endoevaporitic microbial mat. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* 71, 7352–7365. doi:
1493 10.1128/AEM.71.11.7352-7365.2005
- 1494 Sørensen, K., Řeháková, K., Zapomělová, E., Oren, A. (2009). Distribution of benthic phototrophs,
1495 sulfate reducers, and methanogens in two adjacent salt ponds in Eilat, Israel. *Aquat. Microb. Ecol.*
1496 56, 275–284. doi: 10.3354/ame01307
- 1497 Squier, A.H., Hodgson, D.A., and Keely, B.J. (2002). Sedimentary pigments as markers for
1498 environmental change in an Antarctic lake. *Org. Geochem.* 33, 1655–1665. doi: 10.1016/S0146-
1499 6380(02)00177-8

- 1500 Squyres, S.W., Grotzinger, J.P., Arvidson, R.E., Bell, J.F., Calvin, W., Christensen, P.R. *et al.*
1501 (2004). In situ evidence for an ancient aqueous environment at Meridiani Planum, Mars. *Science*
1502 306, 1709–1714. doi: 10.1126/science.1104559
- 1503 Squyres, S.W., Arvidson, R.E., Bell, J.F., Calef, F., Clark, B.C., Cohen, B.A. *et al.* (2012). Ancient
1504 Impact and Aqueous Processes at Endeavour Crater, Mars. *Science*, 336, 570-576, doi:
1505 10.1126/science.1220476
- 1506 Stivaletta, N., and Barbieri, R. (2009). Endolithic microorganisms from spring mound evaporite
1507 deposits (southern Tunisia). *J. Arid Environ.* 73, 33–39. doi: 10.1016/j.jaridenv.2008.09.024
- 1508 Stivaletta, N., López-Gacía, P., Boihem, L., Millie, D.F., and Barbieri, R. (2010). Biomarkers of
1509 endolithic communities within gypsum crusts (southern Tunisia). *Geomicrobiol. J.* 27, 101–110.
1510 doi: 10.1080/01490450903410431
- 1511 Storme, J.Y., Golubic, S., Wilmotte, A., Kleinteich, J., and Velasquez, D. (2015). Raman
1512 characterization of the UV-protective pigment gloeocapsin and its role in the survival of
1513 cyanobacteria. *Astrobiology* 15, 843–857. doi: 10.1089/ast.2015.1292
- 1514 Stromberg, J.M., Applin, D.M., Cloutis, E.A., Rice, M., Berard, G., and Mann, P. (2014). The
1515 persistence of a chlorophyll spectral biosignature from Martian evaporite and spring analogues
1516 under Mars-like conditions. *Int. J. Astrobiol.* 13, 203–223. doi: 10.1017/S1473550413000402
- 1517 Taher, A.G. (2014). Formation and calcification of modern gypsum-dominated stromatolites,
1518 EMISAL, Fayium, Egypt. *Facies* 2014, 721–735. doi: 10.1007/s10347-014-0405-5
- 1519 ten Haven, H.L., de Leeuw, J.W., and Schenck, P.A. (1985). Organic geochemical studies of a
1520 Messinian evaporitic basin, northern Apennines (Italy) I: Hydrocarbon biological markers for a
1521 hypersaline environment. *Geochim. Cosmochim. Acta* 49, 2181–2191. doi: 10.1016/0016-
1522 7037(85)90075-4
- 1523 Testa, G., and Lugli, S. (2000). Gypsum–anhydrite transformations in Messinian evaporites of central
1524 Tuscany (Italy). *Sediment Geol.* 130, 249–268. doi: 10.1016/S0037-0738(99)00118-9
- 1525 Thomas, J.-C., and Geisler, D. (1982). Peuplements benthiques à Cyanophycées des marais salants de
1526 Salin-de-Giraud (Sud de la France). *Géol. Médit.* 9, 391–411. doi: 10.3406/geolm.1982.1217
- 1527 Thomas, J.C. (1984). Formations benthiques à Cyanobactéries des salins de Santa Pola (Espagne):
1528 composition spécifique, morphologique et caractéristiques biologiques des principaux
1529 peuplements. *Rev. Inv. Geol.* 38/39, 139–158.
- 1530 Turich, C., and Freeman, K.H. (2011). Archaeal lipids record paleosalinity in hypersaline systems.
1531 *Org. Geochem.* 42, 1147–1157. doi: 10.1016/j.orggeochem.2011.06.002
- 1532 Turich, C., Freeman, K.H., Bruns, M.A., Conte, M., Jones, A.D., and Wakeham, S.G. (2007). Lipids
1533 of marine Archaea: patterns and provenance in the water-column and sediments. *Geochim.*
1534 *Cosmochim. Acta* 71, 3272–3291. doi: 10.1016/j.gca.2007.04.013

- 1535 Vai, G.B., and Ricci Lucchi, F. (1977). Algal crusts, autochthonous and clastic gypsum in a
1536 cannibalistic evaporite basin: a case history from the Messinian of Northern Apennines.
1537 *Sedimentology* 24, 211–244. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-3091.1977.tb00255.x
- 1538 Van Driessche, A.E.S., Stawski, T.M., and Kellermeier, M. (2019). Calcium sulfate precipitation
1539 pathways in natural and engineered environments. *Chem. Geol.* 530, 119274. doi:
1540 10.1016/j.chemgeo.2019.119274
- 1541 Vandenaabeele, P., Edwards, H.G.M., and Jehlička, J. (2014). The role of mobile instrumentation in
1542 novel applications of Raman spectroscopy: archaeometry, geosciences, and forensics. *Chem. Soc.*
1543 *Rev.* 43, 2628–2649. doi: 10.1039/c3cs60263j
- 1544 Villanueva, J., Grimalt, J.O., de Wit, R., Keely, B.J., and Maxwell, J.R. (1994). Chlorophyll and
1545 carotenoid pigments in solar microbial mats. *Geochim. Cosmochim. Acta* 58, 4703–4715. doi:
1546 10.1016/0016-7037(94)90202-X
- 1547 Vitek, P., and Wierzchos, J. (2020). “Desert biosignatures,” in *Microbial Ecosystems in Central*
1548 *Andes Extreme Environments*, ed. Farías M.E. (Cham, Switzerland: Springer International
1549 Publishing), 73–85.
- 1550 Vitek, P., Jehlička, J., Edwards, H.G.M., and Osterrothová, K. (2009). Identification of β -carotene in
1551 an evaporitic matrix —evaluation of Raman spectroscopic analysis for astrobiological research on
1552 Mars. *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* 393, 1967–1975. doi: 10.1007/s00216-009-2677-0
- 1553 Vitek, P., Cámara-Gallego, B., Edwards, H.G.M., Jehlička, J., Ascaso, C., Wierzchos, J. (2013).
1554 Phototrophic community in gypsum crust from the Atacama desert studied by Raman
1555 spectroscopy and microscopic imaging. *Geomicrobiol. J.* 30, 399–410. doi:
1556 10.1080/01490451.2012.697976
- 1557 Vitek, P., Jehlička, J., Edwards, H.G.M., Hutchinson, I., Ascaso, C., and Wierzchos, J. (2014).
1558 Miniaturized Raman instrumentation detects carotenoids in Mars-analog rocks from the
1559 Mojave and Atacama Desert. *Phil. Trans. R. Soc. A* 372, 20140196. doi:
1560 10.1098/rsta.2014.0196
- 1561 Vitek, P., Ascaso, C., Artieda, O., and Wierzchos, J. (2016). Raman imaging in geomicrobiology:
1562 endolithic phototrophic microorganisms in gypsum from the extreme sun irradiation area in the
1563 Atacama Desert. *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* 408, 4083–4092. doi: 10.1007/s00216-016-9497-9
- 1564 Vitek, P., Ascaso, C., Artieda, O., and Wierzchos, J. (2020). Raman imaging of microbial
1565 colonization in rock-some analytical aspects. *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* 412, 3717–3726. doi:
1566 10.1007/s00216-020-02622-8
- 1567 Vogel, M.B., Des Marais, D.J., Turk, K.A., Parenteau, M.N., Jahnke, L.L., and Kubo, M.D.Y.
1568 (2009). The role of biofilms in the sedimentology of actively forming gypsum deposits at
1569 Guerrero Negro, Mexico. *Astrobiology* 9, 875–893. doi: 10.1089/ast.2008.0325
- 1570 Vogel, M.B., Des Marais, D.J., Parenteau, M.N., Jahnke, L.L., Turk, K.A., and Kubo, M.D.Y.
1571 (2010). Biological influences on modern sulfates: Textures and composition of gypsum deposits
1572 from Guerrero Negro, Baja California Sur, Mexico. *Sed. Geol.* 223, 265–280. doi:
1573 10.1016/j.sedgeo.2009.11.013

- 1574 Volkman, M., Gorbushina, A.A., Kedar, L., and Oren, A. (2006). The structure of euhalothec-362,
1575 a novel red-shifted mycosporine-like amino acid, from a halophilic cyanobacterium (*Euhalotheca*
1576 sp.). *FEMS Microbiol. Lett.* 258, 50–54. doi: 10.1111/j.1574-6968.2006.00203.x
- 1577 Walker, J.J., and Pace, N.R. (2007). Phylogenetic composition of Rocky Mountain endolithic
1578 microbial ecosystems. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* 73, 3497-3504. doi: 10.1128/AEM.02656-06
- 1579 Wang, A., Haskin, L.A., Squyres, S.W., Jolliff, B.L., Crumpler, L., Geller, R. *et al.* (2006). Sulfate
1580 deposition in subsurface regolith in Gusev crater, Mars. *J. Geophys. Res. Planets* 111, E02S17.
1581 doi: 10.1029/2005JE002513
- 1582 Wang, J.S., Suess, E. and Rickert, D. (2004). Authigenic gypsum found in gas hydrate-associated
1583 sediments from Hydrate Ridge, the eastern North Pacific. *Sci. China Ser. D-Earth Sci.* 47, 280–
1584 288. doi: 10.1360/02yd0069
- 1585 Warren, J.K. (1982). The hydrological setting, occurrence and significance of gypsum in late
1586 Quaternary salt lakes in South-Australia. *Sedimentology* 29, 609–637. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-
1587 3091.1982.tb00071.x
- 1588 Warren, J.K. (2010). Evaporites through time: Tectonic, climatic and eustatic controls in marine and
1589 nonmarine deposits. *Earth Sci. Rev.* 98, 217–268. doi: 10.1016/j.earscirev.2009.11.004
- 1590 Warren, J.K. (2016). *Evaporites, A Geological Compendium*, 2nd. ed., Springer.
- 1591 Wierzchos, J., and Ascaso, C. (1994). Application of backscattered electron imaging to the study of
1592 the lichen rock interface. *J. Microsc. Oxford* 175, 54–59.
- 1593 Wierzchos, J., Cámara, B., de los Ríos, A., Davila, A.F., Sanchez Almazo, I.M., Artieda, O., et al.
1594 (2011). Microbial colonization of Ca-sulfate crusts in the hyperarid core of the Atacama Desert:
1595 implications for the search for life on Mars. *Geobiology* 9, 44–60. doi: 10.1111/j.1472-
1596 4669.2010.00254.x
- 1597 Wierzchos, J., DiRuggiero, J., Vítek, P., Artieda, O., Souza-Egipsy, V., Škaloud, P., et al. (2015).
1598 Adaptation strategies of endolithic chlorophototrophs to survive the hyperarid and extreme solar
1599 radiation environment of the Atacama Desert. *Front. Microbiol.* 6, 934. doi:
1600 10.3389/fmicb.2015.00934
- 1601 Wierzchos, J., Casero, M.C., Artieda, O., Ascaso, C. (2018). Endolithic microbial habitats as refuges
1602 for life in polyextreme environment of the Atacama Desert. *Curr. Opin. Microbiol.* 43, 124–131.
1603 doi: 10.1016/j.mib.2018.01.003
- 1604 Wierzchos, J., Artieda, O., Ascaso, C., García, F.N., Vítek, P., Azua-Bustos, A. et al. (2020a).
1605 Crystalline water in gypsum is unavailable for cyanobacteria in laboratory experiments and in
1606 natural desert endolithic habitats. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA* 2020a;117:27786–7. doi:
1607 10.1073/pnas.2013134117
- 1608 Wierzchos, J., Ascaso, C., Artieda, O., and Casero, M.C. (2020b). “The desert polyextreme
1609 environment and endolithic habitats,” in *Microbial Ecosystems in Central Andes Extreme*
1610 *Environments*, ed. Farías M.E. (Cham, Switzerland: Springer International Publishing), 37–50.

- 1611 Wilson, E.O. (2003). *The Future of Life*. New York: Random House. Vintage Books.
- 1612 Winters, Y.D., Lowenstein, T.K., and Timofeeff, M.N. (2013). Identification of carotenoids in
1613 ancient salt from Death Valley, Saline Valley, and Searles Lake, California using laser Raman
1614 spectroscopy. *Astrobiology* 13, 1065–1080. doi: 10.1089/ast.2012.0952
- 1615 Woelfel, J., Sørensen, K., Warkentin, M., Forster, S., Oren, A., and Schumann, R. (2009). Oxygen
1616 evolution in a hypersaline crust: Photosynthesis quantification by *in situ* microelectrode
1617 profiling and planar optodes in incubation chambers. *Aquat. Microb. Ecol.* 56, 263–273.
1618 doi:[10.3354/ame01326](https://doi.org/10.3354/ame01326)
- 1619 Wynn-Williams, D.D., and Edwards, H.G.M. (2000a). Antarctic ecosystems as models for
1620 extraterrestrial surface habitats. *Planet. Space Sci.* 48, 1065–1075. doi: 10.1016/S0032-
1621 0633(00)00080-5
- 1622 Wynn-Williams, D.D., and Edwards, H.G.M. (2000b). Proximal analysis of regolith habitats and
1623 protective biomolecules in situ by laser Raman spectroscopy: Overview of terrestrial Antarctic
1624 habitats and Mars analogs. *Icarus* 144, 486–503. doi: 10.1006/icar.1999.6307
- 1625 Zhao, L., Wang, L., Cernusak, L.A., Liu, X.H., Xiao, H.L., Zhou, M.X., et al. (2016). Significant
1626 difference in hydrogen isotope composition between xylem and tissue water in *Populus*
1627 *euphratica*. *Plant Cell Environ.* 39, 1848–1857. doi: 10.1111/pce.12753
- 1628 Ziolkowski, L.A., Mykytczuk, N.C.S., Omelon, C.R., Johnson, H., Whyte, L.G., and Slater, G.F.
1629 (2013a). Arctic gypsum endoliths: a biogeochemical characterization of a viable and active
1630 microbial community. *Biogeosciences* 10, 7661–7675. doi: 10.5194/bg-10-7661-2013
- 1631 Ziolkowski, L.A., Wierzchos, J., Davila, A.F., and Slater, G.F. (2013b). Radiocarbon evidence of
1632 active endolithic microbial communities in the hyperarid core of the Atacama desert.
1633 *Astrobiology* 13, 607–616. doi: 10.1089/ast.2012.0854
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In review

1645 Table 1 Gypsum colonized by microorganisms in various types of environments

1646

Calcium sulfate-bearing lithic substrate	Locality	Colonization type and position within the rock / colonization depth	Dominant microorganisms detected	References
Gypsum cliff of 90% CaSO ₄ · 2H ₂ O	Harz Mountains, Germany	Endolithic blue-green layer / n.d.	Cyanobacteria - <i>Chroococidiopsis</i> ; occasionally - <i>Nostoc</i> sp. and <i>Oscillatoriales</i> ; heterotrophic bacteria	Boison et al., 2004
Gypsum - selenite	Southern Sicily	Endolithic colonization	Cyanobacteria – <i>Chroococidiopsis</i> , <i>Gloeocapsopsis</i> , <i>Gloeocapsa</i> , <i>Nostoc</i> ; eukaryotic algae	Jehlička et al., 2020
Gypsum - selenite	Southern Sicily	Endolithic colonization	<i>Cyanobacteria</i> - <i>Chroococidiopsis</i> sp., <i>Gloeocapsopsis pleurocapsoides</i> , <i>Gloeocapsa compacta</i> , <i>G. novacekii</i> , <i>G. rupestris</i> , <i>Chroococcus</i> sp., <i>Petalonema</i> sp, <i>Nostoc</i> sp., <i>Gloeobacter violaceus</i> , coccoid algae (Stephanospherinia clade)	Němečková et al., 2023
Gypsum - selenite	Haughton impact crater, Devon Island, Canadian High Arctic	Chasmoendolithic colonization / < 5 mm	<i>Cyanobacteriota</i> - <i>Gloeocapsa</i> , <i>Nostoc</i> and <i>Scytonema</i> ; heterotrophic bacteria	Parnell et al., 2004
Gypsum - selenite	Haughton impact crater,	Endolithic colonization / n.d.	<i>Cyanobacteriota</i> - <i>Gloeocapsa</i> and <i>Nostoc</i> ;	Edwards et al., 2005b

	Devon Island, Canadian High Arctic		heterotrophic bacteria	
Gypsum - selenite	Houghton impact crater, Devon Island, Canadian High Arctic	Endolithic colonization: black regions within the gypsum and close to the surface; green zones associated with scarce pink regions / 2-5 mm	<i>Cyanobacteriota</i> and fungal hyphae (black zone); cyanobacteria - <i>Gloeocapsa</i> / <i>Aphanothece</i> spp. and <i>Chroococciopsis</i> -like, and heterotrophic bacteria (green zone)	Cockell et al., 2010
Gypsum	Gypsum Hill, Canadian High Arctic	Endolithic colonization / 1-5 mm	<i>Cyanobacteriota</i> , algae, fungi and heterotrophic bacteria	Ziolkowski et al., 2013a
Gypsum	Lake St. Martin, Manitoba, Canada	Endolithic colonization / < 30 mm	<i>Chloroflexota</i> , <i>Pseudomonadota</i> , <i>Cyanobacteria</i> , <i>Bacillota</i>	Rhind et al., 2014
Gypsum crusts with quartz grains atop of spring mounds	Southern Tunisia	Endolithic colonization: 5 mm thick green-brown layer beneath the crust surface and sporadic 1-2 mm thick pinkish layer above green-brown layer / < 8 mm	Filamentous and coccoid cyanobacteria and rare algae; heterotrophic bacteria	Stivaletta and Barbieri 2009
Gypsum crusts with quartz grains atop of spring mounds	Southern Tunisia	Endolithic colonization a few millimeters beneath the crust surface: a brown layer (2 mm) lays above the (2 mm) green layer / < 6-8 mm	<i>Cyanobacteriota</i> (<i>Leptolyngbya</i>), <i>Flavobacteria</i> , <i>Actinomycetota</i> , <i>Gammaproteobacteria</i> , <i>Alphaproteobacteria</i> , and <i>Deinococcales</i>	Stivaletta et al., 2010
Soil gypsum crusts	Atacama Desert, north	Endolithic colonization / n.d.	<i>Cyanobacteriota</i> - <i>Chroococciopsis</i> and	Dong et al., 2007

	of the Salar Atacama (Chile), Mojave Desert (U.S.A.) and Al-Jafr Basin (Jordan)		heterotrophic bacteria	
Gypsum/anhydrite crusts on soil surface	Atacama Desert, north of Salar Grande, Chile	Epilithic and endolithic colonization within Ca-sulfate crust and hypoendolithic colonization / < 5 mm	Epilithic lichens and endolithic algae and fungal hyphae (and their associations), cyanobacteria and non-photosynthetic bacteria	Wierzchos et al., 2011, Vitek et al., 2013, Ertekin et al., 2021
Gypsum deposits, gypsum crust	Atacama Desert, Lomas de Tilocalar Atacama and Tarapacá region, Chile	Endolithic colonization / 1-4 mm	Algae, <i>Cyanobacteriota</i> and heterotrophic bacteria	Cámara 2012, Cámara et al., 2016
Gypsum crust on the surface of rhyolite	Atacama Desert, south of Salar Atacama, Chile	Chasmoendolithic colonization / 2-3 mm	<i>Cyanobacteriota</i> - <i>Chroococciopsis</i> and heterotrophic bacteria	DiRuggiero et al., 2013
Gypsum deposits	Atacama Desert, south of Salar Atacama, Chile	Endolithic colonization / n.d.	n.d.	Ziolkowski et al., 2013b
Gypsum/anhydrite crusts on soil surface	Atacama Desert, south of Salar Navidad	Endolithic colonization / < 2 mm	Algae and fungal hyphae, and their associations; cyanobacteria; heterotrophic bacteria	Culka et al., 2017
Gypsum deposits	Atacama Desert, Cordon del Lila, south of Salar Atacama, Chile	Endolithic colonization / 2-6 mm and hypoendolithic colonization / 1-2 mm	Algae, <i>Cyanobacteriota</i> and heterotrophic bacteria	Wierzchos et al., 2015, Casero et al., 2021
Climates: moderate ■ , polar and subarctic ■ , dry arid ■ and dry hyperarid ■				

1647 **Figure captions**

1648 **Figure 1** Selection of areas of colonized gypsum worldwide

1649 Outcrops and similar occurrences (subaerial) (1-37)) (●) ; salars and salterns (subaquatic)(38-45), (■) ;
 1650 other occurrences sabkha (46) (◆) ; gypsum containing inclusions of fossilized microorganisms or
 1651 authigenic biomarkers (47-55) (▲),

1652 More information on sampling sites and their geographic locations can be found in Supplementary
 1653 Data and Supplementary Table S1.

1654 **Figure 2** Examples of gypsum endolithic microbial colonization. A, Gypcrete from the Atacama
 1655 Desert (Cordón de Lila area), later analyzed by Raman imaging where intensity of carotenoid signal
 1656 is visualized in zones rich in algal cells of the *Trebouxiaceae* family (B, C) (adapted from Vitek et
 1657 al., 2016, with permission), the red circles in C point to the regions of Raman analysis); D, bottom
 1658 gypsum specimen with distinct pigmented colonization layers from a solar saltern evaporation pond
 1659 in Eilat, Israel (from Culka et al., 2014, with permission); E, gypsum from Salar de Llamará (from
 1660 Rasuk et al., 2014, with permission); F, gypsum from Lake St. Martin impact structure in Manitoba,
 1661 Canada (adapted from Rhind et al., 2014, with permission); G, H, I: superficial outcrops of colonized
 1662 Messinian selenite gypsum from Santa Nifa, Sicily (adapted from Němečková et al., 2021, with
 1663 permission); the black arrow (a) in I points to black cells of presumably *Gloeocapsa*, whereas the
 1664 yellow arrow (b) points to yellow-brown colonies, presumably *Nostoc*.

1665 **Figure 3.** Examples of microscopy images obtained with different techniques applied for
 1666 visualization of endolithic microbial communities within gypsum substrate from the Atacama Desert
 1667 (panels A, E, I and K-L: endolithic habitats within gypsum crust from Tarapacá and panels B-D, F-H
 1668 and J: endolithic habitats within gypcrete from the Cordón de Lila area respectively). SEM-BSE
 1669 images (A and B) shows disperse cryptoendolithic colonization of pores between gypsum grains by
 1670 algae (*Trebouxia* cells (A) in panel B) and their associated fungal hyphae (H in panel B). SEM-BSE
 1671 image (C) shows algae in close proximity to sepiolite (S). SEM-BSE images (D and E) show
 1672 cryptoendolithic cyanobacteria aggregates and in image E, cyanobacteria (C) and heterotrophic
 1673 bacteria (B). SEM-BSE image (F) shows endolithic filamentous cyanobacterial cells between gypsum
 1674 crystals. Note that molecular biology tools applied to this sample did not detect filamentous
 1675 cyanobacteria. LT-SEM images of cryo-fractured algae cells (panel G) and cyanobacteria cells (panel
 1676 H) with EPS sheaths. ESEM image of hydrated cyanobacteria aggregate (panel I). TEM high-
 1677 resolution image (J) of ultrastructural elements of cyanobacteria cells in close proximity to sepiolite
 1678 (S). MF composed image (K) of autofluorescence of viable algae cells (red signal), remains of algae
 1679 cells (blue signal) and heterotrophic bacteria cells (green signal of SYBR Green II stained cells).
 1680 CLSM 3D reconstruction composed image (L) of autofluorescence of viable algae cells (red signal)
 1681 and heterotrophic bacteria cells (green signal of SYBR Green II stained cells). For materials and
 1682 methods see Wierzchos et al. (2011) and Wierzchos et al. (2015).

1683 **Figure 4. Schematic representation of crypto-, chasmo- and hypsoendolithic habitats within**
 1684 **gypsum deposits from the Atacama Desert.** Modified from Wierzchos et al. (2015) under CC BY
 1685 license.

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1689 **Supplementary Material**

1690 Supplementary Material should be uploaded separately on submission, if there are Supplementary
1691 Figures, please include the caption in the same file as the figure. Supplementary Material templates
1692 can be found in the Frontiers Word Templates file.

1693 Please see the [Supplementary Material section of the Author guidelines](#) for details on the different
1694 file types accepted.

1695 **Supplementary Figure 1.** Results of the statistical data set based on two-samples *t*-test analyses
1696 (ANOVA) of temperature (T) and relative humidity (RH) for two sampling zones with different
1697 climatic regimens in the Atacama Desert. Box plots of relative humidity (RH) (plot A) and
1698 temperature (T) (plot B) are given for two sampling sites: Tarapacá (TRP: KM in Ertekin et al.,
1699 2021) and Cordon Lila – Monturaqui (CL-MTQ in Ertekin et al., 2021). The P_{adj} values from a *t*-test
1700 analysis are shown for data pairs. Significant differences between the data are marked by *** which
1701 indicates P_{adj} value < 0.001. The T and RH data for the Tarapacá zone were collected by J. Wierzchos
1702 from May 2010 to April 2011 and for Cordon Lila – Monturaqui zone from January 2010 to April
1703 2011, respectively.

1704

Figure 1.TIF

Figure 2.JPEG

Figure 3.JPEG

Figure 4.JPEG

